
5G EVE

5G European Validation platform for Extensive trials

Deliverable D3.7

Report on the execution of the interworking
test suites

Project Details

<i>Call</i>	H2020-ICT-17-2018
<i>Type of Action</i>	RIA
<i>Project start date</i>	01/07/2018
<i>Duration</i>	36 months
<i>GA No</i>	815074

Deliverable Details

<i>Deliverable WP:</i>	WP3
<i>Deliverable Task:</i>	Task T3.4
<i>Deliverable Identifier:</i>	5GEVE_D3.7
<i>Deliverable Title:</i>	Report on the execution of the interworking test suites
<i>Editor(s):</i>	Ramón Pérez (TELC)
<i>Author(s):</i>	Ramón Pérez (TELC); Matteo Pergolesi, Francesco Lombardo, Gianluca Reali, Paolo Lungaroni, Stefano Salsano, Nicola Blefari Melazzi (CNIT); Marc Mollà (ERI-ES); Paola Iovanna, Fabio Ubaldi, Anna Sessler (ERI-IT); Gopalasingham Aravinthan (NOK-FR); Giacomo Bernini, Leonardo Agueci, Giada Landi (NXW); Michał Grzesik, Grzegorz Panek (ORA-PL); Juan Rodríguez, Lourdes Luque, Luis Miguel Contreras (TID); Christos Ntogkas, Evangelos Kosmatos, Kostas Trichias, George Makantasis (WINGS)
<i>Reviewer(s):</i>	Jaime García-Reinoso (UC3M), Kostas Trichias (WINGS)
<i>Contractual Date of Delivery:</i>	30/06/2020
<i>Submission Date:</i>	29/06/2020
<i>Dissemination Level:</i>	PU
<i>Status:</i>	Final
<i>Version:</i>	v1.0
<i>File Name:</i>	5GEVE_D3.7_v1.0

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Deliverable History

Version	Date	Modification	Modified by
ToC_v0.1	25/02/2020	<i>ToC proposal, with feedback provided by NOK-FR.</i>	<i>Ramón Pérez.</i>
ToC_v0.2	14/04/2020	<i>Updated ToC with the table to be followed to report the test cases' results.</i>	<i>Ramón Pérez.</i>
v0.3	18/05/2020	<i>First integrated version, with contributions from CNIT, NOK-FR, NXW, ORA-PL, TELC and TID.</i>	<i>Ramón Pérez, based on contributions by CNIT, NOK-FR, NXW, ORA-PL, TELC and TID.</i>
v0.4	01/06/2020	<i>Second integrated version, with contributions from CNIT, ERI-IT and WINGS.</i>	<i>Ramón Pérez, based on contributions by CNIT, ERI-IT and WINGS.</i>
v0.9	10/06/2020	<i>Internal review version, with contributions from CNIT, ERI-ES, ERI-IT, NOK-FR, NXW, ORA-PL, TELC, TID and WINGS.</i>	<i>Ramón Pérez, based on contributions by CNIT, ERI-ES, ERI-IT, NOK-FR, NXW, ORA-PL, TELC, TID and WINGS.</i>
v0.91	22/06/2020	<i>Integration of feedback and comments from internal review.</i>	<i>Ramón Pérez, based on the internal review made by Jaime García-Reinoso (UC3M) and Kostas Trichias (WINGS).</i>
v0.92	25/06/2020	<i>Integration of updates from comments made in the internal review. Document ready for quality checking process.</i>	<i>Ramón Pérez, based on contributions by CNIT, ERI-ES, NOK-FR, NXW, ORA-PL, TELC and TID.</i>
v1.0	26/06/2020	<i>QA review</i>	<i>Kostas Trichias</i>

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

<i>Acronym</i>	<i>Meaning</i>
5G	Fifth Generation
API	Application Programming Interface
ATDD	Acceptance Test Driven Development
CLI	Command Line Interface
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DCM	Data Collection Manager
E2E	End-to-end
EEM	Experiment Execution Manager
ELK	Elasticsearch Logstash Kibana
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FUT	Function Under Test
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
I/W	Interworking
ICMP	Internet Control Message Protocol
ID	Identifier
IP	Internet Protocol
IT	Information Technology
IWF	Interworking Framework
IWL	Interworking Layer
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCM	Lifecycle Management
LO	Local Orchestrator
MANO	Management and Orchestration
Mbps	Megabits per second
MS	Milestone
ms	Milliseconds
MSC	Multi-Site Catalogue
MSI	Multi-Site Inventory
MSNO	Multi-Site Network Orchestrator
MSO-LO	Multi-Site Orchestrator to Local Orchestrator
NBI	Northbound Interface
NFV	Network Function Virtualization

<i>NFVO</i>	NFV Orchestrator
<i>NS</i>	Network Service
<i>NSD</i>	Network Service Descriptor
<i>NSI</i>	Network Service Instance
<i>NSO</i>	Network Service Orchestrator
<i>ONAP</i>	Open Network Automation Platform
<i>OSM</i>	Open Source MANO
<i>PNF</i>	Physical Network Function
<i>PNFD</i>	Physical Network Function Descriptor
<i>RAN</i>	Radio Access Network
<i>RC</i>	Runtime Configurator
<i>REST</i>	Representational State Transfer
<i>RF</i>	Robot Framework
<i>SBI</i>	Southbound Interface
<i>SUT</i>	System Under Test
<i>SW</i>	Software
<i>TOSCA</i>	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
<i>UC</i>	Use Case
<i>VNF</i>	Virtual Network Function
<i>VPN</i>	Virtual Private Network
<i>YAML</i>	YAML Ain't Markup Language

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Executive Summary

Deliverable D3.7 presents the results regarding the execution of the test cases defined in D3.6 [1], in order to validate the features exposed for each component placed in the Interworking (I/W) Framework, possible interconnections between them and aspects related to the system itself; for example, the interconnection between the I/W Framework and each site facility.

This is the final deliverable within task T3.4, related to the Interworking testing process. As a result, this deliverable firstly summarizes and concludes some specific chapters introduced in D3.6 [1], namely an overview of the tests done, a summary of the testing methodology used in the process, an update of the risk plan taking into account the effects caused by the COVID-19, a final specification of the testing roadmap with the corresponding dates in which each milestone has been achieved, and a reminder of the testing tools to be used for performing the tests.

Then, the test results are reported by following a homogeneous format, similar to what was proposed in D3.6 [1]. This is really important in order to be able to analyse the test results with the same criteria for all the cases. In general, what can be extracted from the execution of the test cases reported in this deliverable is that the Interworking Layer is prepared to be deployed and operated in the expected production environment, as most of the components that belong to the IWL have successfully passed their corresponding test suites. However, there are still some test cases to be executed in the near future, as some of them had to be delayed due to several reasons; mainly, due to the COVID-19 situation. These pending test cases will be reported in D3.5 [2] due next year, also coinciding with the final version of the Interworking Layer. To achieve that, a continuous integration process will be followed, and potential failures discovered during the system deployment and the way to solve them will be described in that deliverable.

1 Introduction

Deliverable D3.7 – *Report on the execution of the interworking test suites* represents the second deliverable of Task 3.4 - *Functional testing of interworking capabilities*, whose objective is to present in detail the outcome of all the tests executed with respect to I/W Framework components and capabilities. This deliverable further outlines the overall analysis of the test results.

1.1 Interworking test suites overview

The scope of the I/W Framework testing is to test and validate the I/W Framework itself, as an independent system. As presented in Section 2.3 of D3.6 [1], there are three kind of test categories such as Component Tests (also known as Unit Test to test each components in the I/W Framework), Integration Tests (to test integration between different I/W components) and System Tests (to test the whole I/W Framework), which are proposed to validate the I/W Framework, also aligned with the various testing standards as discussed in Section 2.2 of D3.6 [1].

In Section 3.1 of D3.6 [1], Interworking Framework testing points were identified as the features to be tested with the execution of the different test suites. Depending on the target element that is the objective of the test, the testing points can be determined for both I/W Framework components and capabilities:

- In the case of different components placed in the I/W Framework, i.e. Multi-Site Catalogue, Multi-Site Inventory, Multi-Site Network Orchestrator, Data Collection Manager, Runtime Configurator and Adaptation layer (with the interface from Multi-Site NSO to local Orchestrators), the testing points are identified within the specific Function Under Test (FUT) intended to be studied by Component Tests.
- Regarding the I/W Framework capabilities, the testing points detected are focused mainly on validating the interconnection between different site facilities. In this case, the I/W Framework is considered a System Under Test (SUT) in which these testing points will be tested with the different System Tests defined for that purpose.

In Section 3.2 of D3.6 [1], several tests (as per identified test points) were defined for each test category and in turn each test consists of a set of test suites and test cases. Table 1 summarizes the defined tests and test suites under each test category to validate the features and performance of I/W Framework and its components, while Table 2 describes the test cases related to Integration Tests and Table 3 to System Tests.

Table 1: Summary of I/W Framework Component Tests

Tests	Test Suites	Purpose
Multi-Site Catalogue	Multi-Site Catalogue-NSD Management	<p>The test suites defined several test cases to verify the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An NSD modelling a vertical experiment can be onboarded, updated and deleted in the Multi-Site Catalogue from its NBI as well as the specific per-site OSM orchestrator. • An NSD modelling a single-site service can be successfully onboarded, updated and deleted in the Multi-Site Catalogue through the SBI from a specific per-site OSM orchestrator. • An NSD modelling a vertical experiment can be onboarded, updated and deleted in the Multi-Site Catalogue from its NBI as well as the specific per-site ONAP orchestrator. • An NSD modelling a single-site service can be successfully onboarded, updated and deleted in the Multi-Site Catalogue through the SBI from a specific per-site ONAP orchestrator. • An NSD modelling a vertical experiment can be onboarded, updated and deleted in the Multi-Site Catalogue from its NBI as well as the specific per-site OSM and ONAP orchestrator simultaneously.

	Multi-Site Catalogue-PNFD Management	<p>The test suites defined several test cases to verify the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A PNFD can be successfully onboarded, modified and updated in the Multi-Site Catalogue through the SBI from a specific per-site OSM orchestrator. • A PNFD can be successfully onboarded, modified and deleted in the Multi-Site Catalogue through the SBI from a specific per-site ONAP orchestrator.
	Multi-Site Catalogue-VNF Management	<p>The test suites defined several test cases to verify the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A VNF can be successfully onboarded, modified and updated in the Multi-Site Catalogue through the SBI from a specific per-site OSM orchestrator. • A VNF can be successfully onboarded, modified and updated in the Multi-Site Catalogue through the SBI from a specific per-site ONAP orchestrator.
Multi-Site Inventory	Multi-Site Inventory-Write Operation	<p>The test suites defined several test cases to verify the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The lifecycle management operations related to VNF, PNF and NS Instances: instantiation, scaling, update, termination. • The lifecycle management operations related to composite NS Instances: instantiation, scaling, update, termination.
	Multi-Site Inventory-Query Operation	<p>The test suites defined several test cases to validate the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The parts of the MSI NBI that deals with the retrieval of specific VNF, PNF and NS Instance(s) information. • The parts of the MSI NBI that deals with the retrieval of the full 5G EVE active infrastructure information.
Multi-Site Network Orchestrator	Multi-Site Network Orchestrator	<p>The test suites defined several test cases to validate the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The creation of a NS ID, instantiation of a NS, the management of a NS Lifecycle and operations. • The MSNO notification features.
Data Collection Manager	Data-Collection Manager - Kafka	<p>The test suites defined several test cases to validate the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Kafka cluster availability, so that the rest of depending services and functionalities can make use of it. • The subscribe and unsubscribe operation defined in the Data Collection Manager • If the Data Collection Managers is able deliver the data published in the Kafka bus to the components subscribed to a given topic. • The performance of Kafka cluster in terms of scalability.

	Data-Collection Manager-Kafka-NBI	The test suites intended to verify that Elasticsearch component from the ELK stack is configured for receiving data from Kafka.
	Data-Collection Manager-Kafka-SBI	The test suites intended to verify that Filebeat service is connected to the Kafka cluster and able to react to a file change event and inject a message into the Kafka bus.
Runtime Configurator	Runtime Configurator	<p>The test suites defined several test cases to validate the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the Runtime Configurator is reachable by the Experiment Execution Manager. • The SBI between the Runtime Configurator and the VNFs/PNFs.
Adaptation Layer	Multi-Site NSO to Local Orchestrators interface	<p>The test suites defined several test cases to validate the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The correct retrieval of NFVO information from local database. • The correct retrieval and creation of subscriptions for notifications about the NS instance status. • The request bodies sent to ONAP and OSM NBI interface are correct. The responses from ONAP and OSM are handled correctly. The responses returned by MSO API are correct.

Table 2: Summary of Integration Tests between Interworking Framework Components

Tests	Test Suites	Purpose
Multi-Site Network Orchestrator and Multi-Site Catalogue	Integration test will be based on the Multi-Site Network Orchestrator component tests, but also integrating the Multi-Site Catalogue for the tests	The integration tests are required for some integration points in order to verify that the I/W Framework is working as expected. However, most of the I/W components tests listed in Table 1 require the integration between several components to validate their functionality (e.g. the specific integration test between Adaptation Layer and Multi Site NSO is not needed since the Adaptation Layer component test requires integration with the Multi-Site NSO).

Table 3: Summary of I/W Framework System Tests

Tests	Test Suites	Purpose
Site facilities' interconnection	Site facilities' interconnection	<p>The test suites defined several test cases to validate the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If all the sites are reachable from the Turin site, where the I/W Framework is to be installed. If desired from any other site, the operation would be totally equivalent. • To ensure that the 5G EVE Web Portal is reachable from the Turin site, where the I/W Framework is to be installed. • Method to measure the delay and capacity between Turin and another site at any precise moment.

1.2 Document objectives

The objectives covered in this deliverable are the following:

1. Complete some pending chapters presented in D3.6 [1], such as the risk plan or the testing roadmap.
2. Report the results on the execution of the test suites, following a homogeneous format to execute the tests, and publishing the results in a specific repository.
3. Analyse the results obtained by the test suites' execution and extract some conclusions based on that.

This deliverable is aligned with D3.4 [3], in terms of the status of the different I/W Framework components. However, there are some tests that have not been covered in this deliverable, which will be addressed in D3.5 [2], coinciding with the final version of the Interworking Framework.

1.3 Document structure

The rest of this document is organized as follows:

- In **Section 2**, the final specifications of the Interworking testing suites are included, covering several points that are further developed over D3.6 [1]. In this section, a summary of the test cases, testing methodology and testing tools will be given, and it will also include the update of the risk plan and the testing roadmap.
- **Section 3** provides the results obtained by the execution of test cases related to the Interworking Framework, separating them in the three main categories defined in D3.6 [1]: Component Tests, Integration Tests (between these I/W Framework components in which it makes sense to do this) and System Tests (mainly related to site facilities' interconnection).
- An analysis of the results obtained in the previous section is presented in **Section 4**, including the acceptance criteria used to validate if a test has been passed or not (pass/fail), an overall test assessment for the three tests' categories and an evaluation of the impact produced by the test environment.
- Finally, **Section 5** presents the conclusions extracted from all the information included in this deliverable, regarding the execution of test cases.

2 Interworking testing suites final definition

2.1 Testing methodology and strategy

As detailed in D3.6 [1], the testing of I/W Framework followed some software testing principles and strategies present in most software development projects along with ETSI standard specifications. Table 4 summarizes the positioning of I/W Framework testing methodology according to software testing methodologies.

Table 4: Positioning Interworking Framework testing methodology according to software testing methodologies

Option	I/W Framework position
<i>Design-space exploration/In vivo testing</i>	""In vivo testing using stubs
<i>Module vs. system testing</i>	Both are used at two levels: FUT an SUT
<i>Types of tests</i>	Mainly functional tests
<i>Automated vs. manual testing</i>	Both, automated testing using Robot Framework [4]
<i>Microservices vs. Monoliths</i>	Micro-services
<i>Waterfall vs. agile</i>	Both
<i>Open-source vs. closed-source</i>	Open-source

As described in D3.6 [1], the scope of the I/W Framework testing is to test and validate the framework itself, as an independent system. We performed integration test with other 5G EVE components, like the Portal components and the 5G EVE site NFV-Os, but E2E validation of the 5G EVE platform is not in the scope of this deliverable and it will be reported in the Milestone reports.

There are three main categories of tests suites executed to validate the I/W Framework aligned with the test plan already summarized in D3.6 [1]:

- The **Component Tests** (also known as Unit Test), mandatory for all the I/W Framework components, are the main kind of tests defined in the Interworking test suites and are oriented to test each FUT (or testing points related to specific components) of the I/W Framework separately.
- The **Integration Tests** for testing and validating the different connections between components of the I/W Framework in which a specific interaction may be required.
- The **System Tests** are intended to validate the whole I/W Framework system (i.e. SUT), with all the components already deployed in the production environment.

The I/W Framework Components Tests, or Unit Tests, require integration between various components to validate their functionality. So, the I/W Framework Component Tests already cover most of the integration test scope. The execution of a set of Integration Tests between the Multi-Site NSO to the Multi-Site Catalogue is the only Integration Test executed specifically under the scope of Integration Tests.

Since there is a high level of interconnectivity between I/W Framework component using REST APIs, API testing tools are used. Among the list of state-of-the-art API testing tools, Robot Framework [4] has been selected and used for execution of automated testing.

2.2 Overview of tests already performed

The overview of I/W Framework test suites and their corresponding tests have been already presented in section 1.1. This section summarizes the different tests executed (results will be presented in section 3) as well as the tests that will be performed later in the project, which will be covered in D3.5 [2].

Table 5: Summary of tests related to Component Tests

Tests	Test Suites	Tests already performed	Tests still to be done (D3.5 [2])
Multi-Site Catalogue	Multi-Site Catalogue-NSD Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NSD Onboarding to single site – OSM NSD Deletion to single site – OSM NSD Onboarding from single site – OSM NSD Deletion from single site – OSM NSD Onboarding to multiple sites – OSM and ONAP NSD Deletion to multiple sites – OSM and ONAP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NSD Update to single site – OSM NSD Update from single site – OSM NSD Onboarding to single site – ONAP NSD Update from single site – ONAP NSD Deletion to single site – ONAP NSD Onboarding from single site – ONAP NSD Update from single site – ONAP NSD Deletion from single site – ONAP NSD Update to multiple sites – OSM and ONAP
	Multi-Site Catalogue-VNF Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> VNF Onboarding from site – OSM VNF Deletion from site - OSM 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> VNF Update from site – OSM VNF Onboarding from site – ONAP VNF Update from site – ONAP VNF Deletion from site - ONAP
	Multi-Site Catalogue-PNFD Management	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PNFD Onboarding from site – OSM PNFD Update from site – OSM PNFD Deletion from site – OSM PNFD Onboarding from site – ONAP PNFD Update from site – ONAP PNFD Deletion from site – ONAP
Multi-Site Inventory	Multi-Site Inventory-Write Operation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NSI instantiation at single site NSI termination at single site Non-existing NSI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NSI scaling at single site NSI update at single site Composite NSI instantiation Composite NSI scaling Composite NSI update Composite NSI termination
	Multi-Site Inventory-Query Operation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NSI status Infrastructure status 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Non-existing NSI status

Multi-Site Network Orchestrator	Multi-Site Network Orchestrator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network Service ID creation • Network Service instantiation • Network Service Lifecycle Management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NS Lifecycle management operations • NS Lifecycle Management notifications
Data Collection Manager	Data-Collection Manager - Kafka	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kafka cluster setup • Subscribe operation • Publish operation • Unsubscribe operation • Stress test 	-
	Data-Collection Manager-Kafka-NBI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kafka-Elasticsearch configuration 	-
	Data-Collection Manager-Kafka-SBI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kafka-Beats service availability • File change event leads to Kafka message 	-
Runtime Configurator	Runtime Configurator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NBI Interface • SBI Interface • Complete workflow 	-
Adaptation Layer	MSO-LO – Configuration MSO-LO-Turin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NFVO information integration test • OSM driver integration test • ONAP driver integration test 	-
	MSO-LO – Configuration MSO-LO-Turin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NFVO information integration test • Subscriptions for notifications integration test • OSM driver integration test • ONAP driver integration test 	-
	MSO-LO – Configuration MSO-LO-Ever	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EVER driver Test Unit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EVER driver Integration • EVER site integration

Table 6: Summary of tests related to Integration Tests

Tests	Test Suites	Tests already performed	Tests still to be done (D3.5 [2])
Multi-Site Network Orchestrator and Multi-Site Catalogue¹	Multi-Site Network Orchestrator-Catalogue	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network Service ID creation • Network Service instantiation • Network Service Lifecycle Management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network Service Lifecycle Management notifications

¹ As explained in section 3.2.3.1, the same tests used in the MSNO Component tests are also used for the Integration tests between the MSNO and the MSC.

Table 7: Summary of tests related to System Tests

Tests	Test Suites	Tests already performed	Tests still to be done (D3.5 [2])
Site facilities' inter-connection	IWL – French Site	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ping Test between French site and Turin Lab (IWL) • Iperf Test between French site and Turin Lab (IWL) 	-
	IWL – Spanish Site	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ping Test between Spanish site and Turin Lab (IWL) • Iperf Test between Spanish site and Turin Lab (IWL) 	-
	IWL – Italian Site	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ping Test between Rome/Turin site and Turin Lab (IWL) • Iperf Test between Rome/Turin site and Turin Lab (IWL) 	-
	IWL – Greek Site	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ping Test between Greek site and Turin Lab (IWL) • Iperf Test between Greek site and Turin Lab (IWL) 	-

2.3 Risk plan update

Risk plan has been already defined and described in previous deliverable D3.6 [1]. This chapter is an update in the context of risk mitigation and action plan.

As was described in D3.6 [1], some identifiers to manage risks, action and mitigation plans were introduced. There are built in the following way:

$$\{\text{NAME}\}\{\text{X}\}\{\text{Y}\}\{\text{Z}\}$$

where:

NAME – category of identifiers; possible values: RISK for identify a risk, MPLAN for mitigation plan or ACTION_PLAN for action plan,

X – number of key feature,

Y – category of scenario; possible values: a – single site or b – multi site,

Z – id number.

In the beginning of 2020, the coronavirus pandemic impacted several aspects of our work. To meet project expectations and, at the same time, take into account pandemic restrictions, new subchapter with COVID-19 risks has been prepared.

2.3.1 Final risk plan

2.3.1.1 Risks identified in single-site scenarios

Table 8: Single-site scenario risk related to Orchestration Plane Interworking (I)

Key features	Category	Brief Description	Risk	Priority	Mitigation	Action	Probability
<i>Orchestration Plane Interworking</i>	Connectivity	Low bandwidth performance.	RISK1a_001	High	MPLAN1a_001	ACTION_PLAN1a_001	Medium

MPLAN1a_001:

- (1) Policies and Procedures: Define the frequency of latency and bandwidth tests with scenarios.
- (2) Documentation: Create and publish documentation about networking configuration.
- (5) Configuration management: Allocate additional 25 % of bandwidth than required during configuration process. Minimum value of allocated bandwidth shouldn't be lower than 100 Mbps.
- (10) Technical controls: Monitor bandwidth and latency (run tests). Report and store results.

ACTION_PLAN1a_001:

- Increase allocated bandwidth by minimum 25%. Rerun testes and analyse results. If needed increase the frequency of bandwidth and latency tests.
- Check networking configuration and make some changes if needed. Rerun tests and analyse results.

Table 9: Single-site scenario risk related to Orchestration Plane Interworking (II)

Key features	Category	Brief Description	Risk	Priority	Mitigation	Action	Probability
<i>Orchestration Plane Interworking</i>	Connectivity	High latency. Messages not in order.	RISK1a_002	Medium	MPLAN1a_002	ACTION_PLAN1a_002	Low

MPLAN1a_002:

- (1) Policies and Procedures: Define the frequency of latency and bandwidth tests with scenarios.
- (2) Documentation: Create and publish documentation about networking configuration.
- (5) Configuration management: Allocate additional 25 % of bandwidth than required during configuration process. Minimum value of allocated bandwidth mustn't be lower than 100 Mbps.
- (10) Technical controls: Monitor bandwidth and latency (run tests). Report and store results.

ACTION_PLAN1a_002:

- Increase allocated bandwidth by minimum 25%. Rerun testes and analyse results. If needed increase the frequency of bandwidth and latency tests.
- Check networking configuration and make some changes if needed. Rerun tests and analyse results.

Table 10: Single-site scenario risk related to Experiment Monitoring Support (I)

Key features	Category	Brief Description	Risk	Priority	Mitigation	Action	Probability
<i>Single-site Experiment Monitoring Support</i>	Monitoring	Mismatch between monitoring tools (because of using different tools)	RISK2a_001	Low	MPLAN 2a_001	ACTION_PLAN 2a_001	Medium

MPLAN2a_001:

(1) Policies and Procedures: Define universal metrics/KPI and implement/use it in allowed monitoring tools. Use (if needed implement) some tools to convert results to supported format.

(2) Documentation: Draw up a list of all allowed tools for site facility. Reduce the number of used solutions to only required (minimum).

ACTION_PLAN2a_001:

- Use available/implemented tools to convert results to supported format.
- If no converter exists, implement a new dedicated tool.

Table 11: Single-site scenario risk related to Experiment Monitoring Support (II)

Key features	Category	Brief Description	Risk	Priority	Mitigation	Action	Probability
<i>Single-site Experiment Monitoring Support</i>	Monitoring	Mismatch between monitoring tools (because of using different versions)	RISK2a_002	Medium	MPLAN 2a_002	ACTION_PLAN 2a_002	Low

MPLAN2a_002:

(1) Policies and Procedures: Prepare a procedure to update tool version. Test the new tool version (stability and compatibility) in development environmental.

(5) Configuration management: Plan and update tools in time when no experiments are running. Create a backup of tools (for each version with settings), test backups.

(6) Version Control: Draw up a list of currently tool versions in utilization. Verify the compliance of tools versions regularly.

ACTION_PLAN2a_002:

- Back to previous compliant tool version.
- Develop update or fix the bugs. If needed report problems to tool's developer/owner.

Table 12: Single-site scenario risk related to Experiment Monitoring Support (III)

Key features	Category	Brief Description	Risk	Priority	Mitigation	Action	Probability
<i>Single-site Experiment Monitoring Support</i>	Monitoring	Some monitoring tools need to be manually executed	RISK2a_003	Medium	MPLAN 2a_003	ACTION_PLAN 2a_003	Medium

MPLAN2a_003:

- (1) Policies and Procedures: Draw up and publish test executions instructions.
- (4) Separation of duties: Appoint staff responsible for tests execution.
- (3) Training: Train procedures regularly.

ACTION_PLAN2a_003:

- Update tests procedures.
- Appoint new staff members responsible for tests execution. Organize additional training sessions.

Table 13: Single-site scenario risk related to Applications Deployment Support (I)

Key features	Category	Brief Description	Risk	Priority	Mitigation	Action	Probability
<i>Single-site Applications Deployment Support</i>	Operation	Local orchestrator is different from one site to the other	RISK3a_001	High	MPLAN 3a_001	ACTION_PLAN 3a_001	Medium

MPLAN3a_001:

- (1) Policies and Procedures: Draw up common deployment procedures with messages schemas, workflows etc.
- (2) Documentation: Draw up and publish a local orchestrator documentation.
- (5) Configuration management: Define and implement interfaces used to application deployment inside the site facilities. Use ETSI interfaces specification.

ACTION_PLAN3a_001:

- Fix the local orchestrator interface or implement additional component to adjust interface to required specification.

Table 14: Single-site scenario risk related to Applications Deployment Support (II)

Key features	Category	Brief Description	Risk	Priority	Mitigation	Action	Probability
<i>Single-site Applications Deployment Support</i>	Operation	Local orchestrator is not able to reach other orchestrators	RISK3a_002	Medium	MPLAN 3a_002	ACTION_PLAN 3a_002	Medium

MPLAN3a_002:

(1) Policies and Procedures: Draw up communications procedures between orchestrators with messages schemas, workflows, etc.

(2) Documentation: Draw up and publish a local orchestrator documentation.

(5) Configuration management: Define and implement interfaces and workflows between orchestrators. Use ETSI interfaces specification.

ACTION_PLAN3a_002:

- Fix the local orchestrator interface or implement additional component to adjust interface to required specification.

Table 15: Single-site scenario risk related to Network Automation Support (I)

Key features	Category	Brief Description	Risk	Priority	Mitigation	Action	Probability
<i>Single-site Network Automation Support</i>	Operation	Capability to deploy the required connectivity services (first phase). Different local controllers; different network infrastructure	RISK4a_001	Low	MPLAN 4a_001	ACTION_PLAN 4a_001	Low

MPLAN4a_001:

(2) Documentation: Draw up and publish networks infrastructure documentation.

(5) Configuration management: Define and implement network configuration and infrastructure. Create and store a backup of network configuration.

(10) Technical controls: Review network configuration and infrastructure regularly.

ACTION_PLAN4a_001:

- Fix the network infrastructure or configuration.

Table 16: Single-site scenario risk related to Network Automation Support (II)

Key features	Category	Brief Description	Risk	Priority	Mitigation	Action	Probability
<i>Single-site Network Automation Support</i>	Operation	Capability to deploy the required slices (second phase) to the requested site. Slicing support in the network but the specification for some slice is not possible.	RISK4a_002	Low	MPLAN 4a_002	ACTION_PLAN 4a_002	Low

MPLAN4a_002:

(2) Documentation: Draw up some basic requirements for slicing and implement it in sites facilities.

(5) Configuration management: Draw up a slice configuration compatible with site's use cases and define basic requirements.

ACTION_PLAN4a_002:

- Fix the slice configuration.

2.3.1.2 Risks identified in multi-site scenarios**Table 17: Multi-site scenario risks related to Control Plane Interworking**

Key features	Category	Brief Description	Risk	Priority	Mitigation	Action	Probability
<i>Control Plane Interworking</i>	Connectivity	Low bandwidth performance but secure connectivity among sites for control traffic.	RISK1b_001	High	MPLAN 1b_001	ACTION_PLAN 1b_001	Medium
			RISK1b_002	Medium			Medium

MPLAN1b_001:

(1) Policies and Procedures: Define the frequency of latency and bandwidth tests with scenarios. Draw up secure connectivity requirements and supported solutions.

(2) Documentation: Create and publish documentation about sites networking interconnections.

(5) Configuration management: Allocate additional 25 % of bandwidth than required during configuration process. Minimum value of allocated bandwidth between sites shouldn't be lower than 100 Mbps.

(10) Technical controls: Monitor bandwidth and latency (run tests). Report and store results.

ACTION_PLAN1b_001:

- Increase allocated bandwidth by minimum 25%. Rerun testes and analyse results. If needed increase the frequency of bandwidth and latency tests.
- Check networking configuration and if need make some changes. Rerun tests and analyse results.

Table 18: Multi-site scenario risks related to Data Plane Interworking

Key features	Category	Brief Description	Risk	Priority	Mitigation	Action	Probability
<i>Data Plane Interworking</i>	Conne- tivity	Secure connectivity among sites for user traffic. Low bandwidth performance experiments will employ best effort connectivity. High bandwidth performance experiments will employ a parallel high bandwidth low latency network, which will be available at least between two sites.	RISK2b_001	Low	MPLAN 2b_001	ACTION_ PLAN 2b_001	High
			RISK2b_002	Medium			High

MPLAN2b_001:

(1) Policies and Procedures: Define the scenarios and frequency of latency and bandwidth tests. Draw up a secure connectivity requirements and supported solutions.

(2) Documentation: Create and publish documentation about networking configuration.

(5) Configuration management: Allocate additional 25 % of bandwidth than required during configuration process. Minimum value of allocated bandwidth between sites should not be lower than 100 Mbps.

(10) Technical controls: Monitor bandwidth and latency (run tests) and security level of connection. Report and store results.

ACTION_PLAN2b_001:

- Increase allocated bandwidth by minimum 25%. Rerun tests and analyse results. If needed increase the frequency of bandwidth and latency tests.
- Check networking configuration and if needed make some changes. Set up new secure network connections adjusted to experiments requirements. Rerun tests and analyse results.

Table 19: Multi-site scenario risks related to Experiment Monitoring Support

Key features	Category	Brief Description	Risk	Priority	Mitigation	Action	Probability
<i>Multi-site Experiment Monitoring Support</i>	Monitoring	Capability of translating the monitoring requirements defined by experimenters (based on selected KPIs) to the sites taking part in the same experiment. Sites will typically have different local monitoring tools and mechanisms.	RISK3b_001	High	MPLAN 3b_001	ACTION_PLAN 3b_001	Low
			RISK3b_002	Medium			Low

MPLAN3b_001:

(1) Policies and Procedures: Define universal metrics/KPI and implement/use it in supported monitoring tools for each site. Prepare a universal format to define experiment requirements and present results - use (if needed implement) some tools to convert data to supported format.

(2) Documentation: Draw up and share a list of all supported tools (with requirements) for each site facility. Define the tools which should be used in multi-site experiments.

ACTION_PLAN3b_001:

- Use available/implemented tools to convert data to supported format.
- If no converter exists, implement a new dedicated tool.

Table 20: Multi-site scenario risks related to E2E Orchestration Support

Key features	Category	Brief Description	Risk	Priority	Mitigation	Action	Probability
<i>Multi-site E2E Orchestration Support</i>	Operation	Capability to deploy the required slices, and VNFs hosted in the 5G-EVE Catalogue on top of them, to the sites taking part in the same experiment. Sites will typically have different local orchestrators, controllers and network infrastructure.	RISK4b_001	Low	MPLAN 4b_001	ACTION_PLAN 4b_001	High
			RISK4b_002	Low			High

MPLAN4b_001:

(2) Documentation: Draw up some basic requirements for slicing on multi-site level and implement it in sites facilities. Draw up and publish a local orchestrator documentation.

(5) Configuration management: Define and implement interfaces and workflows between orchestrators and between orchestrators and catalogue. Use ETSI interfaces specification.

ACTION_PLAN4b_001:

- Fix the local orchestrator interface or slice configuration within site facility. If needed implement additional component to adjust interfaces to required specifications.

2.3.2 COVID-19 risk plan**2.3.2.1 COVID-19 risks identified in single-site scenarios****Table 21: Risks related to COVID-19 in single-site scenarios**

Risk Number	Brief description	Impact	Priority	Mitigation	Level
1	Access Restrictions to 5G-EVE sites	Delay in infrastructure upgrades	Medium	Focus more on SW upgrades	Medium
2	Interconnection activities require some IT staff availability	Delay in interconnecting all components within sites	Medium	Remote debug action	Low
3	UC testing requires some SW and HW components deployed in sites	Delay, some testing is not possible	High	Reschedule physical actions and prioritize remote actions	High

2.3.2.2 COVID-19 risks identified in multi-site scenarios**Table 22: Risks related to COVID-19 in multi-site scenarios**

Risk Number	Brief description	Impact	Priority	Mitigation	Level
1	Access Restrictions to 5G-EVE sites	Possible delay, end to end integration testing is not possible	High	Focus on SW tests, expand them or define a new one (more detailed), validate interfaces of components to minimize possible problems in integration	High
2	Inter-site connectivity is not in place	Possible delay, end to end testing is not possible	High	Local deployments of portal and I/W Framework	High

3	MS8 integration still testing	Reduced capacity for MS9 development of isolated islands	High	Postpone some features after MS9 (D3.5 [2])	High
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2.4 Testing roadmap

The initial I/W framework testing roadmap is already presented in D3.6 [1] as aligned with the roadmap of delivery included in D3.3. The updated testing roadmap along with completed tests and future tests to be reported in D3.5 [2] are presented below in Table 23.

Table 23: Interworking testing roadmap

Test	Type	Completed Test Suites	Date
Multi-Site Catalogue	Unit Test	Multi-Site Catalogue has been validated against ETSI OSM local-site orchestrators.	01/04/2020
Multi-Site Inventory	Unit Test	Multi-Site Inventory write operations i.e. validated the Multi-Site NSO write/updated operation to Multi-Site Inventory after the instantiation of the NS.	05/05/2020
Multi-Site Network Orchestrator	Unit Test	Unit testing for all services and features required for the selected use cases.	03/12/2019
Data Collection Manager	Unit Test	Unit tests related to Kafka functionality, NBI for Kafka and ELK Interconnection, SBI for Kafka and Filebeat interconnection	25/09/2019
Runtime Configuration	Unit Test	Unit tests related to NBI, SBI and complete workflow.	03/04/2020
Adaptation Layer	Unit Test	The Multi-Site NSO to local Orchestrator interface (MSO-LO) for ONAP and OSM. Unit testing of various features of adaptation layer such as NS instance management, NS LCM management	19/02/2020
MSNO - MSC	Integration Test	Basic integration for supported UC in Turin.	24/01/2020
Interworking Framework	System Test	Single-site testing, focused on selected UC.	10/06/2020

2.5 Testing environment and selected tools

As previously mentioned, the tests that will be conducted are Component tests, Integration tests and System tests. That practically means that all the components of the Interworking Layer will be tested both for their standalone operation as well as the integration with the rest of the components and their behaviour as a system. For that to be possible, all the components will need to be deployed in the same testing environment. For the testing process to allow more flexibility on the partners working on each component, the testing environment has been duplicated on the Spanish and the Italian site facility since most, if not all, of the components have been originally developed and deployed there. After verifying the correct implementation and behaviour of all the IWL components, the system or some of the components can be deployed in any site if needed.

Due to the high intensity of interactions needed between the various components, all the functionalities are provided using REST APIs. In order to test all the available APIs, an API testing tool will be used. A wide list of such tools is available online such as Robot Framework [4], Selenium [5], Cucumber [6], Pytest [7], Junit

[8], Katalon Studio [9] and more. Since the early stages of the project, Robot Framework [4] has been selected and used for execution automation and testing. Also, since most of the partners have some previous experience with it, that is the tool of choice to handle the IWL components testing.

Robot Framework [4] is a generic test automation framework for acceptance testing and acceptance test-driven development (ATDD). It is a keyword-driven testing framework that uses a simple tabular test data syntax, an example of which is shown in Figure 1, to define and execute a wide range of tests. Robot Framework [4], except from its role as the API testing tool, is currently an internal component of the EEM in order to automate the experiment execution process.

```
resource.robot 3
1  *** Settings ***
2  Documentation      A resource file with reusable keywords and variables.
3  ...
4  ...
5  ...                The system specific keywords created here form our own
6  ...                domain specific language. They utilize keywords provided
7  ...                by the imported Selenium2Library.
8  Library            Selenium2Library
9
10 *** Variables ***
11 ${SERVER}          systemundertest.companyxyz.co.nz
12 ${BROWSER}         Firefox
13 ${DELAYO}          0
14 ${DELAY1}          1
15 ${DELAYS}          5
16 ${VALID USER}     UserX
17 ${VALID PASSWORD} PasswordXYZ
18 ${LOGIN URL}       http://${SERVER}/access/login/
19 ${HOME URL}        http://${SERVER}/Home/
20 ${INVALID ALERT}  Invalid login details, please try again
21 ${EMPTY ALERT}    There should be no empty fields, please try again
22
23 *** Keywords ***
24 Open Browser To Login Page
25   Open Browser      ${LOGIN URL}    ${BROWSER}
26   Maximize Browser Window
27   Set Selenium Speed  ${DELAYO}
28   Login Page Should Be Open
29
30 Login Page Should Be Open
31   Title Should Be    SUI | Company XYZ Login Page
32
33 Go To Login Page
34   Go To              ${LOGIN URL}
35   Login Page Should Be Open
36
37 Input Username
38   [Arguments]        ${username}
```

Figure 1: Example of Robot Framework [4] script

An important feature of Robot Framework [4] is the automatic generation of detailed reports for the executed tests, an example of which can be seen in Figure 2, containing a great level of detail regarding each specific action's results and any logging information generated by that action. This feature is extremely valuable for the debugging process in case of test failures.

Figure 2: Example of Robot Framework [4] output

Some of the components in the IWL, in order to be tested, required additional tools, such components are the DCM and the RC. In order to test the operation of the DCM, a deployment of Apache Kafka [10] and Apache ZooKeeper [11] is necessary in the testing environment. These tools implement the message broker of the platform responsible for collecting the metrics and KPIs and also conveying signalling messages to the components. In order to reduce the resource requirements for this testing deployment, a deployment in Docker [12] containers was selected as the best solution. This deployment is used as a separate testing deployment independent of the platform’s actual message broker.

In the case of the RC, a deployment of Ansible [13] is required in the testing environment. Ansible [13] is an open-source software provisioning, configuration management, and application-deployment tool. It provides a simple syntax using YAML to define the actions to be automated.

Using playbooks, like the one in Figure 3, the test developer can describe any and all actions and scenarios that require testing with a great level of detail. It also provides a detailed output for all the performed actions, as seen in Figure 4.

Some of the actions performed by Ansible [13] are the Day-2 configuration of the VNFs as well as any actions described in the test case scenario like managing traffic generators, configuring applications, modifying element behaviour and more. Currently, Ansible [13] is an internal component of the RC that handles all the operations aforementioned.

```

1 ---
2 ▾ - hosts: webservers
3   sudo: yes
4
5   vars:
6     app_name: PleaseDeployMe
7     repo_url: https://github.com/username/repo_name.git
8     repo_remote: origin
9     repo_version: master
10    webapps_dir: /deployed
11    virtualenv_root: /deployed/PleaseDeployMe/mac
12 ▾ tasks:
13
14 ▾ - name: git pull project
15   git: repo={{repo_url}} dest={{webapps_dir}}/{{app_name}} version=master
16
17   notify:
18     - restart app
19
20 ▾ - name: install things
21   pip: name=virtualenv
22
23 ▾ - name: create virtualenv
24   command: virtualenv /deployed/PleaseDeployMe/venv
25
26 ▾ - name: activate virtualenv
27   command: /bin/bash /deployed/PleaseDeployMe/venv/bin/activate
28
29 ▾ - pip: requirements=/deployed/{{app_name}}/requirements.txt virtualenv=/deployed/{{app_name}}/mac
30
31 ▾ - name: run supervisor
32   command: "supervisord -c /deployed/PleaseDeployMe/supervisord.conf"
33
34 ▾ - name: begin flask app
35   supervisorctl: name=flask_app state=started
36
37
38 ▾ handlers:
39 ▾ - name: restart app
40   supervisorctl: name={{app_name}} state=restarted
41
42

```

Figure 3: Example of Ansible [13] playbook

```

PLAY [ubuntu3,centos3] *****
TASK [Gathering Facts] *****
ok: [ubuntu3]
ok: [centos3]

TASK [Set our installation variables for CentOS] *****
skipping: [ubuntu3]
ok: [centos3]

TASK [Set our installation variables for Ubuntu] *****
skipping: [centos3]
ok: [ubuntu3]

TASK [Show pre-set distribution based facts] *****
ok: [ubuntu3] => {
  "msg": "webserver_application_port:8080 webserver_application_path:/local/nginx webserver_application_user:nginx"
}
ok: [centos3] => {
  "msg": "webserver_application_port:80 webserver_application_path:/usr/share/www webserver_application_user:root"
}

PLAY RECAP *****
centos3      : ok=3    changed=0    unreachable=0    failed=0
ubuntu3     : ok=3    changed=0    unreachable=0    failed=0

```

Figure 4: Example of Ansible [13] playbook output

3 Test suites result report and analysis

3.1 Reporting format

The results of the execution of the test cases will be reported in two different formats:

- Using **tables** which will follow the specific format shown in . In this repository, there are three main folders, related to the three main test categories covered in this testing process (i.e. Component, Integration and System tests). Each of them has different sub-folders containing each entity involved.
- Table 24 and including the following fields:
 - Name of the test component and test suite: lists the name of the component and title of the test suites
 - Test title/<Test ID>: each test suite consists of a set of tests specified by a title and an ID.
 - Test purpose: describes the aim of the test.
 - Test tools: tools used for executing the tests (Robot Framework [4] is commonly used as an automated testing tool).
 - Result: outlines the test results
 - Comments/Details: any further comments or details apart from what is described in the Result field
- The test cases execution are uploaded on a specific Github repository, available here: <https://github.com/5GEVE/D3.7-Test-Suites-Results>. In this repository, there are three main folders, related to the three main test categories covered in this testing process (i.e. Component, Integration and System tests). Each of them has different sub-folders containing each entity involved.

Table 24: Table format to report the execution of test cases

Name of the Component and Test Suite	
Test 1 title	<Test ID>
Test purpose	Summary of what is included in D3.6 [1]. If there are some modifications, include them here.
Test tools	Tools used for executing the test.
Result	Passed/Failed/[Other].
Comments	Comments related to the test that are interesting to be shared.
Details	Specific details that should be mentioned.
Test N title	<Test ID>
Test purpose	Summary of what is included in D3.6 [1]. If there are some modifications, include them here.
Test tools	Tools used for executing the test.
Result	Passed/Failed/[Other].
Comments	Comments related to the test that are interesting to be shared.
Details	Specific details that should be mentioned.

3.2 Interworking Framework Component Tests

3.2.1 Multi-Site Catalogue test suites

The Multi-Site Catalogue tests aim at validating the main features and functionalities related to the management of Networks Service Descriptors (NSDs), VNF Descriptors (VNFDs) and PNF Descriptors (PNFDs) that can be used by the 5G EVE Portal for the provisioning of single-site and multi-site vertical experiments. As central

repository of the 5G EVE Interworking Framework, the Multi-Site Catalogue collect the capabilities offered by the site facilities and exposed them to the 5G EVE portal through a common model. From D3.6 [1], all of the tests defined in the test plan were classified as functional, and had the main objective to validate the behaviour of the Multi-Site Catalogue for the onboarding and management of NSDs and VNFDs in compliance with the ETSI NFV SOL specifications and the workflows defined in D3.3 [14].

3.2.1.1 Test configuration, scenario and execution

The Multi-Site Catalogue tests carried out so far have been performed in two main setups:

- Manual tests executed by triggering operations through CLI and web GUIs of the Multi-Site Catalogue and the local site orchestrators.
- Automated tests executed with Robot Framework [4].

All of the Multi-Site Catalogue tests have been performed in two main relevant test environments: the Nextworks lab, and the Interworking Framework setup in Turin.

In both cases the same test configurations have been used, as depicted in Figure 5. The tests related to single site catalogue have been executed with the setup shown in Figure 5a, with Robot Framework [4] (or CLIs and GUIs in case of manual tests) as test system interacting with the Multi-Site Catalogue instance and the single local site orchestrator to trigger the test actions and verify the results. On the other hand, the tests related to multi-site operations have been performed with the setup shown in Figure 5b, with two local site orchestrators to represent a multi-site scenario.

Figure 5: Multi-Site Catalogue test configuration

3.2.1.2 Test results

The following tables provides a summary of the Multi-Site Catalogue test results (covering both single-site and multi-site operations), following the template described in section 3.1 and the test plan reported in D3.6 [1]. Up to now, the Multi-Site Catalogue has been validated against ETSI OSM local site orchestrators only, as the support and integration with ONAP local site orchestrators is still in progress at the time of writing, and planned to be finalized not before Q2-2020 (i.e. not in time to report tests in this document). Therefore, those tests planned in D3.6 [1] for validating the catalogue functionalities with ONAP local site orchestrators will reported in the final D3.5 [2] deliverable.

As the information for manual and automated tests results is practically the same, and to avoid duplication of information, the tables provide details for the automated tests executed with Robot Framework [4]. In addition, the Robot Framework [4] tests source code, together with the outputs generated when executing each test are available at:

https://github.com/5GEVE/D3.7-Test-Suites-Results/tree/master/component_tests/multi_site_catalogue/

Table 25: Multi-Site Catalogue - NSD Management test results

Multi-Site Catalogue – NSD Management	
Test 1 - NSD Onboarding to single site - OSM	
Nsd-onboard-single-site-to-osm	
<i>Test purpose</i>	This test aims at verifying that an NSD modelling a vertical experiment (in TOSCA format) can be successfully onboarded in the Multi-Site Catalogue from its NBI and delivered to a specific per-site OSM orchestrator.
<i>Test tools</i>	Robot Framework [4]
<i>Result</i>	Passed
<i>Comments</i>	-
<i>Details</i>	-
Test 2 - NSD Update to single site - OSM	
Nsd-update-single-site-to-osm	
<i>Test purpose</i>	This test aims at verifying that an existing NSD modelling a vertical experiment can be modified in the Multi-Site Catalogue from its NBI and updated in a specific per-site OSM orchestrator.
<i>Test tools</i>	-
<i>Result</i>	Not executed
<i>Comments</i>	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet implemented. Planned for Q3-2020
<i>Details</i>	-
Test 3 - NSD Deletion to single site - OSM	
Nsd-delete-single-site-to-osm	
<i>Test purpose</i>	This test aims at verifying that an existing NSD modelling a vertical experiment can be deleted in the Multi-Site Catalogue from its NBI and removed from a specific per-site OSM orchestrator.
<i>Test tools</i>	Robot Framework [4]
<i>Result</i>	Passed
<i>Comments</i>	-
<i>Details</i>	-
Test 4 - NSD Onboarding from single site - OSM	
Nsd-onboard-single-site-from-osm	
<i>Test purpose</i>	This test aims at verifying that an NSD modelling a single-site service can be successfully onboarded in the Multi-Site Catalogue through the SBI from a specific per-site OSM orchestrator.
<i>Test tools</i>	Robot Framework [4]
<i>Result</i>	Passed
<i>Comments</i>	-
<i>Details</i>	-
Test 5 - NSD Update from single site - OSM	
Nsd-update-single-site-from-osm	
<i>Test purpose</i>	This test aims at verifying that an existing NSD modelling a single site service (previously onboarded from a per-site OSM orchestrator) can be modified in the Multi-Site Catalogue from its SBI when it is updated in the original per-site OSM orchestrator.
<i>Test tools</i>	-
<i>Result</i>	Not executed
<i>Comments</i>	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet implemented. Planned for Q3-2020

<i>Details</i>	-
Test 6 - NSD Deletion from single site - OSM	Nsd-delete-single-site-from-osm
<i>Test purpose</i>	This test aims at verifying that an existing NSD modelling a per-site service (previously onboarded from a per-site OSM orchestrator) can be deleted in the Multi-Site Catalogue from its SBI when it is removed in the original per-site OSM orchestrator.
<i>Test tools</i>	Robot Framework [4]
<i>Result</i>	Passed
<i>Comments</i>	-
<i>Details</i>	-
Test 7 - NSD Onboarding to single site - ONAP	Nsd-onboard-single-site-to-onap
<i>Test purpose</i>	This test aims at verifying that an NSD modelling a vertical experiment (in TOSCA format) can be successfully onboarded in the Multi-Site Catalogue from its NBI and delivered to a specific per-site ONAP orchestrator.
<i>Test tools</i>	-
<i>Result</i>	Not executed
<i>Comments</i>	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet fully implemented. Planned for late Q2-2020
<i>Details</i>	-
Test 8 - NSD Update from single site - ONAP	Nsd-update-single-site-to-onap
<i>Test purpose</i>	This test aims at verifying that an existing NSD modelling a vertical experiment can be modified in the Multi-Site Catalogue from its NBI and updated in a specific per-site ONAP orchestrator.
<i>Test tools</i>	-
<i>Result</i>	Not executed
<i>Comments</i>	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet fully implemented. Planned for late Q2-2020
<i>Details</i>	-
Test 9 - NSD Deletion to single site - ONAP	Nsd-delete-single-site-to-onap
<i>Test purpose</i>	This test aims at verifying that an existing NSD modelling a vertical experiment can be deleted in the Multi-Site Catalogue from its NBI and removed from a specific per-site ONAP orchestrator.
<i>Test tools</i>	-
<i>Result</i>	Not executed
<i>Comments</i>	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet fully implemented. Planned for late Q2-2020
<i>Details</i>	-
Test 10 - NSD Onboarding from single site - ONAP	Nsd-onboard-single-site-from-onap
<i>Test purpose</i>	This test aims at verifying that an NSD modelling a single-site service can be successfully onboarded in the Multi-Site Catalogue through the SBI from a specific per-site ONAP orchestrator.
<i>Test tools</i>	-
<i>Result</i>	Not executed
<i>Comments</i>	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet fully implemented. Planned for late Q2-2020
<i>Details</i>	-

Test 11 - NSD Update from single site - ONAP		Nsd-update-single-site-from-onap
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that an existing NSD modelling a single site service (previously onboarded from a per-site ONAP orchestrator) can be modified in the Multi-Site Catalogue from its SBI when it is updated in the original per-site ONAP orchestrator.	
Test tools	-	
Result	Not executed	
Comments	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet fully implemented. Planned for late Q2-2020	
Details	-	
Test 12 - NSD Deletion from single site - ONAP		Nsd-delete-single-site-from-onap
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that an existing NSD modelling a per-site service (previously onboarded from a per-site ONAP orchestrator) can be deleted in the Multi-Site Catalogue from its SBI when it is removed in the original per-site ONAP orchestrator.	
Test tools	-	
Result	Not executed	
Comments	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet fully implemented. Planned for late Q2-2020	
Details	-	
Test 13 - NSD Onboarding to multiple sites – OSM and ONAP		Nsd-onboard-multiple-site-to-osm-onap
Test purpose	This test aimed originally (i.e. as per D3.6 [1]) at verifying that an NSD modelling a vertical experiment (in TOSCA format) can be successfully onboarded in the Multi-Site Catalogue from its NBI and delivered simultaneously to specific per-site OSM and ONAP orchestrators.	
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]	
Result	Passed	
Comments	As the Multi-Site Catalogue full support of ONAP local site orchestrators is planned to be completed not before late Q2-2020, the test purpose has been temporarily updated to simultaneous onboard an NSD to two different per-site OSM orchestrators. This version of the test is anyway enough to validate the NSD onboarding to multiple sites.	
Details	-	
Test 14 - NSD Update to multiple sites – OSM and ONAP		Nsd-update- multiple-site-to-osm-onap
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that an existing NSD modelling a vertical experiment can be modified in the Multi-Site Catalogue from its NBI and updated simultaneously in the specific per-site OSM and ONAP orchestrators.	
Test tools	-	
Result	Not executed	
Comments	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet implemented. Planned for Q3-2020	
Details	-	
Test 15 - NSD Deletion to multiple sites – OSM and ONAP		Nsd-delete- multiple-site-to-osm-onap
Test purpose	This test aimed originally (i.e. as per D3.6 [1]) at verifying that an existing NSD modelling a vertical experiment can be deleted in the Multi-Site Catalogue from its NBI and removed simultaneously from the specific per-site OSM and ONAP orchestrators.	
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]	
Result	Passed	

Comments	As the Multi-Site Catalogue full support of ONAP local site orchestrators is planned to be completed not before late Q2-2020, the test purpose has been temporarily updated to simultaneous delete an NSD in to two different per-site OSM orchestrators. This version of the test is anyway enough to validate the NSD deletion to multiple sites.
Details	-

Table 26: Multi-Site Catalogue - VNF Management test results

Multi-Site Catalogue – VNF Management	
Test 1 - VNF Onboarding from site - OSM	
	vnf-onboard-from-osm
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that a VNF can be successfully onboarded in the Multi-Site Catalogue through the SBI from a specific per-site OSM orchestrator.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	Passed
Comments	-
Details	-
Test 2 - VNF Update from site - OSM	
	vnf-update-from-osm
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that an existing VNF can be modified in the Multi-Site Catalogue through the SBI from a specific per-site OSM orchestrator.
Test tools	-
Result	Not executed
Comments	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet implemented. Planned for Q3-2020
Details	Robot Framework [4]
Test 3 - VNF Deletion from site - OSM	
	vnf-delete-from-osm
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that an existing VNF can be deleted in the Multi-Site Catalogue through its SBI from a specific per-site OSM orchestrator.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	Passed
Comments	-
Details	-
Test 4 - VNF Onboarding from site - ONAP	
	vnf-onboard-from-onap
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that a VNF can be successfully onboarded in the Multi-Site Catalogue through the SBI from a specific per-site ONAP orchestrator.
Test tools	-
Result	Not executed
Comments	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet fully implemented. Planned for late Q2-2020
Details	-
Test 5 - VNF Update from site - ONAP	
	vnf-update-from-onap
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that an existing VNF can be modified in the Multi-Site Catalogue through the SBI from a specific per-site ONAP orchestrator.
Test tools	-
Result	Not executed

Comments	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet fully implemented. Planned for late Q2-2020
Details	-
Test 6 - VNF Deletion from site - ONAP	
	vnf-delete-from-onap
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that an existing VNF can be deleted in the Multi-Site Catalogue through its SBI from a specific per-site ONAP orchestrator.
Test tools	-
Result	Not executed
Comments	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet fully implemented. Planned for late Q2-2020
Details	-

Table 27: Multi-Site Catalogue – PNFD Management test results

Multi-Site Catalogue – PNFD Management	
Test 1 - PNFD Onboarding from site - OSM	
	pnfd-onboard-from-osm
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that a PNFD can be successfully onboarded in the Multi-Site Catalogue through the SBI from a specific per-site OSM orchestrator.
Test tools	-
Result	Not executed
Comments	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet fully implemented. Planned for late Q3-2020
Details	-
Test 2 - PNFD Update from site - OSM	
	pnfd-update-from-osm
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that an existing PNFD can be modified in the Multi-Site Catalogue through the SBI from a specific per-site OSM orchestrator.
Test tools	-
Result	Not executed
Comments	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet fully implemented. Planned for late Q3-2020
Details	-
Test 3 - PNFD Deletion from site - OSM	
	pnfd-delete-from-osm
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that an existing PNFD can be deleted in the Multi-Site Catalogue through its SBI from a specific per-site OSM orchestrator.
Test tools	-
Result	Not executed
Comments	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet fully implemented. Planned for late Q3-2020
Details	-
Expected results	This test aims at verifying that a PNFD can be successfully onboarded in the Multi-Site Catalogue through the SBI from a specific per-site OSM orchestrator.
Test 4 - PNFD Onboarding from site - ONAP	
	pnfd-onboard-from-onap
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that a PNFD can be successfully onboarded in the Multi-Site Catalogue through the SBI from a specific per-site ONAP orchestrator.
Test tools	-
Result	Not executed

Comments	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet fully implemented. Planned for late Q3-2020	
Details	-	
Test 5 - PNFD Update from site - ONAP		pnfd-update-from-onap
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that an existing PNFD can be modified in the Multi-Site Catalogue through the SBI from a specific per-site ONAP orchestrator.	
Test tools	-	
Result	Not executed	
Comments	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet fully implemented. Planned for late Q3-2020	
Details	-	
Test 6 - PNFD Deletion from site - ONAP		pnfd-delete-from-onap
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that an existing VNF can be deleted in the Multi-Site Catalogue through its SBI from a specific per-site ONAP orchestrator.	
Test tools	-	
Result	Not executed	
Comments	Multi-Site Catalogue feature not yet fully implemented. Planned for late Q3-2020	
Details	-	

3.2.1.3 Result analysis

The Multi-Site Catalogue test plan, as described in the previous section, is composed by a total of 27 test cases (15 for NSD Management, 6 for VNF Management and 6 for PNFD Management). Out of these 27 Multi-Site Catalogue planned tests, 8 have been successfully performed, while the rest are still in not executed status. While it is clear that is pre-mature to draw conclusions and provide a comprehensive results analysis, it is surely possible to state that these 8 tests validate the key Multi-Site Catalogue operations and functionalities. Indeed, besides the low execution rate (around 30%) of the tests, the results reported in the section 3.2.1.2 above show that the relevant features have been successfully tested, and enable a full use of the Multi-Site Catalogue within the I/W framework first, and the whole 5G EVE platform as well. The Multi-Site Catalogue is indeed involved in both the experiment design/preparation phase, as the 5G EVE Portal access the catalogue for retrieving the site capabilities in terms of VNFs and Network Services to build end-to-end vertical experiments, and the experiment deployment phase, when the Multi-Site Network Orchestrator retrieves information about NSDs to instantiate. In practice, the key relevant catalogue features for NSD management (NSD onboarding and deletion to and from local site orchestrators) and VNF management (VNF onboarding and deletion) are fully functional and successfully tested against the ETSI OSM local orchestrators, which assess the integration with 3 out of 4 5G EVE site facilities (i.e. the Italian, Spanish and Greek sites). In addition, NSD onboarding to multiple sites is also successfully validated, with two instances of ETSI OSM local site orchestrators (still representing a realistic 5G EVE scenario, e.g. considering the wide use of ETSI OSM). However, as said above, part of the NSD and VNF management tests has not been executed as they involve the integration of the Multi-Site Catalogue with ONAP local site orchestrators, that is currently under finalization and is reported as an important achievement for the I/W framework capabilities in D3.4 [3]. Details about the execution of these tests will be reported in D3.5 [2].

In addition, few other of the NSD and VNF management features and planned tests have not been executed, with reference to descriptors update and PNFD management operations. In the overall Multi-Site Catalogue development and integration planning (and taking into account the requirements from the 5G EVE vertical experiments and the integration with the 5G EVE Portal for the first two years of the project), these features have been assigned with a lower priority (against the key catalogue features for NSD and VNF management previously mentioned) and are planned to be completed and released during Q3-2020. Details about the execution of the related tests will be also reported in D3.5 [2].

3.2.2 Multi-Site Inventory test suites

As stated in deliverable D3.6 [1], the initial approach for the Multi-Site Inventory is that it stores information about active Network Services in the 5G EVE infrastructure. In that Deliverable, a broader test plan was included, considering also VNFs and PNFs, to account for future extensions. However, in this document, tests reports are exclusively focused on the NS related operations, since those are the ones that are supported today. Of course, stored information about NSs includes all the details of the VNFs/PNFs forming them.

There are two classes of operations:

- Write in the Inventory, accessible only to the Multi-Site NSO.
- Query to the Inventory, accessible to the Multi-Site NSO and potentially also to other components like the Portal.

It is worth commenting that “Write” operations will be associated to a single NS, while the “Query” may be referred to a single NS, or to the full list of stored NSs.

3.2.2.1 Test configuration, scenario and execution

The test scenario (Figure 6) was already depicted in deliverable D3.6 [1] and it has not changed. The implementation of the Inventory is very tightly coupled with that of the NSO, so both provide a common external testing API as a unique system, triggering the operations mentioned above.

Figure 6: Multi-Site Inventory test scenario

The test plan has been covered by means of Robot Framework [4] test scripts, which also allows for automated testing in conjunction with Jenkins.

Tests have been executed in the 5TONIC lab, where instances of the Multi-Site NSO and Multi-Site Inventory are already operational. Since 5TONIC is a multi-domain site (i.e., it includes more than one orchestrator), even those tests involving composite NS have been executed there.

3.2.2.2 Test results

The following tables provide all the details regarding the testing of the Multi-Site Inventory features, following the templates described in section 3.1, and based on the test plan in D3.6 [1]. In that document, tests related to (composite) NSI were grouped in a single test case; in this section we have included one test case per lifecycle operation, so results are better understood. The only new tests relate to what happens when an operation over a non-existing NSI is executed, trying to ensure correct error handling. Full specifications for these tests, equivalent to that of D3.6 [1], are included in Annex A. Tests related to VNFs and PNFs have not been covered in this deliverable, only focusing on the NSIs ones.

It is also worth noticing that, differently from the Multi-Site Catalogue testing, these operations are totally equivalent independently of the Local NFVO(s) that is(are) triggered by the Multi-Site NSO, so there is no need to replicate tests for OSM and ONAP.

Finally, the “Query” operation does not need to be particularized for single-site or composite NSs, since the operation responds with all the information available independently on the type of NS.

Table 28: Multi-Site Inventory - Write Operation test results

Multi-Site Inventory – Write Operation	
Test 1 - NSI instantiation at single site	
	write-nsi-lifecycle-single-site-instance
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that after the Multi-Site NSO instantiates a NS in a single site, it correctly updates the Multi-Site Inventory, creating a new entry. The entry must include all the information related to the NS, in particular, its VNFs/PNFs and Virtual Links.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	Passed
Comments	-
Details	-
Test 2 - NSI scaling at single site	
	write-nsi-lifecycle-single-site-scale
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that after the Multi-Site NSO scales a NS in a single site, it correctly updates the appropriate existing entry at the Multi-Site Inventory.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	-
Comments	Not in scope in this IWL version
Details	-
Test 3 - NSI update at single site	
	write-nsi-lifecycle-single-site-update
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that after the Multi-Site NSO updates a NS in a single site, it correctly updates the appropriate existing entry at the Multi-Site Inventory.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	-
Comments	Not in scope in this IWL version
Details	-
Test 4 - NSI termination at single site	
	write-nsi-lifecycle-single-site-delete
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that after the Multi-Site NSO terminates a NS in a single site, it correctly deletes the appropriate existing entry at the Multi-Site Inventory.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	Passed
Comments	-
Details	-
Test 5 - Composite NSI instantiation	
	write-nsi-lifecycle-composite-instance
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that after the Multi-Site NSO instantiates a composite NS in at least two sites, it correctly updates the Multi-Site Inventory, creating a new entry. The entry must include all the information related to the NS, in particular, its VNFs/PNFs and Virtual Links, and at which site they are deployed.

Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	-
Comments	Not in scope in this IWL version
Details	-
Test 6 - Composite NSI scaling	
	write-nsi-lifecycle-composite-scale
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that after the Multi-Site NSO scales a composite NS, it correctly updates the appropriate existing entry at the Multi-Site Inventory.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	-
Comments	Not in scope in this IWL version
Details	-
Test 7 - Composite NSI update	
	write-nsi-lifecycle-composite-update
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that after the Multi-Site NSO updates a composite NS, it correctly updates the appropriate existing entry at the Multi-Site Inventory.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	-
Comments	Not in scope in this IWL version
Details	-
Test 8 - Composite NSI termination	
	write-nsi-lifecycle-composite-delete
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that after the Multi-Site NSO terminates a composite NS, it correctly deletes the appropriate existing entry at the Multi-Site Inventory.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	-
Comments	Planned in Roadmap
Details	-
Test 9 - Non-existing NSI	
	write-nsi-lifecycle-non-existing
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that appropriate error handling is done in case the Multi-Site NSO tries an operation over a non-existing NSI index at the Multi-Site Inventory.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	Passed
Comments	-
Details	-

Table 29: Multi-Site Inventory - Query Operation test results

Multi-Site Inventory – Query Operation	
Test 1 - NSI status	
	query-nsi-status
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that after the Multi-Site NSO requests the information for an existing NSI, the Multi-Site Inventory provides such information, including the forming VNFs/PNFs and Virtual Links.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]

Result	Passed
Comments	-
Details	-
Test 2 - Infrastructure status	
	query-infrast-status
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that after the Multi-Site NSO requests the information for all existing NSIs, the Multi-Site Inventory provides such information, including the forming VNFs/PNFs and Virtual Links of each of the NSs. The response when there are no active NSIs yet has to be checked as well.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	Passed
Comments	-
Details	-
Test 3 - Non-existing NSI status	
	query-non-existing
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying that appropriate error handling is done in case the Multi-Site NSO requests information about a non-existing NSI index at the Multi-Site Inventory.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	To be executed
Comments	-
Details	-

3.2.2.3 Result analysis

The results confirm the correct implementation of the Multi-Site Inventory according to the development roadmap. Some features of ETSI NFV SOL 005 interface are not implemented yet as they are not required in the scope of the 5G-EVE project.

3.2.3 Multi-Site Network Orchestrator test suites

The Multi-Site Network Orchestrator is the component in charge of onboarding and deploying Network Services into the 5G-EVE sites. As described in D3.2 [15] and D3.3 [14], it offers a north-bound interface for the management of the Network Services Life Cycle (NS LCM) based on the specifications from ETSI NFV SOL 005.

The MSNO interacts with the Multi-Site Catalogue, the IWL Site Inventory and the MSO-LO (Adaptation Layer) for handling the NS LCM operations (please, refer to D3.4 [3] for more information)

3.2.3.1 Test configuration, scenario and execution

All tests described here are executed using Robot Framework [4] scripts. We aim to reuse the same tests for component and integration testing. For that reason, we prepared two scenarios:

- MSNO integrated with MSC and MSO-LO mock simulators, for the component test.
- MSNO integrated with the rest of IWL components and with a real site NFV-O, for the integration tests.

3.2.3.2 Test results

Following we detail the results of the MSNO testing.

Table 30: Multi-Site Network Orchestrator test results

Multi-Site Network Orchestrator	
Test 1 - Network Service ID creation	
	ms-nso-id-creation
Test purpose	The purpose of this test is to validate the creation of a Network Service ID. This is the first step for deploying a Network Service in 5G-EVE
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	Passed
Comments	The original design of this test assumed that the onboarding of a NS into the IWL will raise an onboarding in the 5G-EVE sites. In the final implementation the onboarding of the NS into the sites is done in the Instantiation operation and for this reason the checking is moved to Test 2
Details	-
Test 2 – Network Service instantiation	
	ms-nso-ns-inst
Test purpose	This test aims to verify the instantiation of a Network Service in a specific 5G-EVE site
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	Passed
Comments	-
Details	-
Test 3 – Network Service Lifecycle Management	
	ms-nso-ns-lcm
Test purpose	The purpose of this test is to validate the lifecycle management of the Network Services.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	Passed
Comments	Some features included in this test are not supported yet, like update and scale operations. They are postponed.
Details	-
Test 4 – NS Lifecycle management operations	
	ms-nso-ns-lcm-op
Test purpose	The purpose of this test is to validate the LCM operations of the NS LCM.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	Not executed
Comments	This test contains operations that are not in the scope of the IWL development so at the moment of generating this deliverable, we did not execute them.
Details	-
Test 5 – Network Service Lifecycle Management notifications	
	ms-nso-ns-lcm-not
Test purpose	The purpose of this test is to validate the MSNO notifications.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	Not Executed
Comments	These tests are planned in roadmap, to be executed when IWL supports external notifications.
Details	-

3.2.3.3 Result analysis

The Multi-Site Network Orchestrator is one of the main components of the Inter-Working Layer. It interacts with the rest of the components (Multi-Site Inventory, Multi-Site Catalogue, IWL Repository, Adaptation Layer) and it provides service to other IWL components and 5G-EVE Portal components. For this reason, it is essential to have a good component testing of the MSNO to guarantee the right performance before initiating the integration effort.

Robot Framework [4] tests allows us to define comprehensive testing scenarios that cover not only the best case scenarios but also, they cover failing cases that might introduce errors in the other components. A part of this, Robot Framework [4] execution can be automated and in the case of the MSNO, we introduce it in the continuous integration chain so every time we change a line of code we execute all tests for guarantee that we do not break the backward compatibility.

The component test results show that MSNO follows the standards and internal specifications and it is ready for being integrated with other components.

3.2.4 Data Collection Manager test suites

The Data Collection Manager component is the central module of the Monitoring architecture deployed in 5G EVE, implementing a publish-subscribe system to deliver the metrics' and KPIs' values generated during a specific experiment to the entities that consume that data.

Regarding the I/W Framework testing process, as it only involves the testing of the IWL in an isolated way, without interacting with other layers such as the 5G EVE Portal, the tests defined for this component try to verify the basic functionalities offered by the DCM and also to test the resiliency of the platform by performing specific load and stress tests, in order to confirm that this kind of platforms will allow the expected workload that will be present in the production system.

3.2.4.1 Test configuration, scenario and execution

In terms of configuration, the scenario is exactly the same than presented in D3.6 [1], only including Robot Framework [4] for automatically execute the test suites defined.

3.2.4.2 Test results

The results obtained in the execution of the DCM test suites are the following:

Table 31: Data Collection Manager - Kafka test results

Data Collection Manager – Kafka	
Test 1 - Kafka cluster setup	dcm-cluster-setup
<i>Test purpose</i>	This test aims at validating the Kafka cluster availability, so that the rest of depending services and functionalities can make use of it.
<i>Test tools</i>	Robot Framework [4], Kafka [10] and ZooKeeper [11]
<i>Result</i>	Passed.
<i>Comments</i>	Changes in server.properties file: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • listeners=PLAINTEXT://0.0.0.0:9092 • advertised.listeners=PLAINTEXT://<KAFKA_IP>:9092 • delete.topic.enable=true • auto.create.topics.enable=false
<i>Details</i>	-
Test 2 - Subscribe operation	dcm-subscribe

Test purpose	This test intends to emulate the subscribe operation defined in the Data Collection Manager, which involves the creation of a topic and the setup of a process in the Kafka cluster which starts listening to that topic.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4], Kafka [10] and ZooKeeper [11]. Postman for sending requests to the Data Collection and Storage, which interacts with the Data Collection Manager. These requests are handled by a Python script.
Result	Passed.
Comments	<p>Tested with signalling topics. This is the result:</p> <pre>testbed@dcm-dcs-dv-5g-eve ~/kafka/kafka_2.12-2.4.1 \$ bin/kafka-topics.sh --list --zookeeper 10.9.8.203:2181</pre> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • signalling.kpi • signalling.metric.application • signalling.metric.infrastructure
Details	-
Test 3 - Publish operation	
	dcm-publish
Test purpose	The purpose of this test is to verify that the Data Collection Manager is able to deliver the data published in the Kafka bus to the components subscribed to a given topic.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4], Kafka [10] and ZooKeeper [11]. Postman for sending requests to the Data Collection Manager. These requests are handled by a Python script.
Result	Passed.
Comments	<p>Tested with signalling topics. Delivered data is the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Action = subscribe: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ "{\"topic\": \"asti.spain.metric.application.cpu\", \"action\": \"subscribe\", \"expId\": \"asti\"}" ○ "{\"topic\": \"asti.spain.metric.application.deviation\", \"action\": \"subscribe\", \"expId\": \"asti\"}" ○ "{\"topic\": \"asti.spain.metric.application.latency\", \"action\": \"subscribe\", \"expId\": \"asti\"}" • Action = unsubscribe: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ "{\"topic\": \"asti.spain.metric.application.cpu\", \"action\": \"unsubscribe\", \"expId\": \"asti\"}" ○ "{\"topic\": \"asti.spain.metric.application.deviation\", \"action\": \"unsubscribe\", \"expId\": \"asti\"}" ○ "{\"topic\": \"asti.spain.metric.application.latency\", \"action\": \"unsubscribe\", \"expId\": \"asti\"}"
Details	-
Test 4 - Unsubscribe operation	
	dcm-unsubscribe
Test purpose	This test performs the unsubscribe operation defined in the Data Collection Manager, in order to test the successful withdrawal of a given topic.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4], Kafka [10] and ZooKeeper [11]. Postman for sending requests to the Data Collection and Storage, which interacts with the Data Collection Manager. These requests are handled by a Python script.
Result	Passed.
Comments	Tested with signalling topics. Topics are deleted correctly.
Details	-
Test 5 - Stress test	
	dcm-stress

Test purpose	As the Data Collection Manager is a central component in the 5G EVE architecture, it is needed to verify its correct performance in terms of scalability. For that reason, his test is defined in order to execute a stress test for validating that the Kafka cluster is able to manage a huge amount of data and topics concurrently.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4], Dockerized testbed with Kafka [10] and ZooKeeper [11]. Sangrenel [16] is used for executing load tests in Kafka. Docker [12] stats command for obtaining resource consumption in Docker [12] containers. ELK stack is used for receiving the data generated by Sangrenel [16] and delivered by Kafka [10].
Result	Passed.
Comments	Load testing results are currently private results, which are expected to be exposed in specific scientific papers. Tests have been performed with a different number of topics (from a single topic case to multi-topic cases, testing with 140 topics simultaneously as the most demanding case. Each experiment consumes nearly 100 Mbps of monitoring data. Latency is nearly 5-10 ms for the publishers, and CPU consumption must be taken into consideration in the Kafka server (at least 8 cores are needed in order not to lose performance).
Details	The results of this test case are not available in the Github repository. The main results and conclusions extracted from this test case can be found in [17].

Table 32: Data Collection Manager – NBI test results

Data Collection Manager – Kafka-ELK interconnection – NBI	
Test 1 - Kafka-Elasticsearch configuration	dcm-nbi-elk-config
Test purpose	This test intends to verify that Elasticsearch component from the ELK Stack [18] is configured for receiving data from Kafka.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4], Dockerized testbed with Kafka [10], ZooKeeper [11] and ELK [18].
Result	Passed.
Comments	This test is executed for the building of the Dockerized environment. Check this repository: https://github.com/5GEVE/5geve-wp4-monitoring-dockerized-env
Details	-

Table 33: Data Collection Manager - SBI test results

Data Collection Manager – Kafka-Filebeat interconnection – SBI	
Test 1 - Kafka-Beats service availability	dcm-sbi-filebeat-status
Test purpose	This test is intended to verify that Filebeat [19] service is connected to the Kafka cluster.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4], Dockerized testbed with Kafka [10], ZooKeeper [11] and ELK [18]. Filebeat [19] service installed in a different server.
Result	Passed.
Comments	This test is executed for the building of the Dockerized environment. Check this repository: https://github.com/5GEVE/5geve-wp4-monitoring-dockerized-env
Details	-
Test 2 - File change event leads to Kafka message	dcm-sbi-filebeat-event
Test purpose	The purpose of this test is to verify that that Filebeat [19] is able to react to a file change event and inject a message into the Kafka bus.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4], Kafka [10] and ZooKeeper [11]. Filebeat [19] service installed in a different server.
Result	Passed.

Comments	After deploying Filebeat [19], the server handled by it was changed and Filebeat [19] automatically sends to Kafka [10] the updated file.
Details	-

3.2.4.3 Result analysis

The results obtained were the expected ones, as Kafka [10] is a tool implemented in a multitude of production systems with very good performance. Probably the most critical test was Test 5 related to the DCM – Kafka test suites, which involved the stress test to confirm that the DCM would be able to handle the amount of data expected during the test executions, which was confirmed in the end based on the presented results, which were also published in a specific paper [17].

3.2.5 Runtime Configurator test suites

The Runtime Configurator is the entity from the I/W Framework in charge of handling the execution of commands in the targeted servers of a given experiments to perform a set of operations related to the Experiment Execution workflow, such as the configuration of the infrastructure component or the applications that are going to be used in a given experiment (also called Day-2 Configuration process) or the execution of specific commands related to each step of the test execution.

In that way, the testing process that involves the Runtime Configurator are mainly focused on checking that the interaction between possible external entities (mainly, the Experiment Execution Manager) and Ansible, which is the core component within the RC, works, and also confirming that the RC is able to reach specific VNFs and to execute some commands on them.

3.2.5.1 Test configuration, scenario and execution

In terms of configuration, the scenario is exactly the same than presented in D3.6 [1], only including Robot Framework [4] for automatically execute the test suites defined.

3.2.5.2 Test results

The results obtained in the execution of the RC test suites are the following:

Table 34: Runtime Configurator test results

Runtime Configurator	
Test 1 – NBI Interface	rc-nbi-if
Test purpose	The objective of this test is to verify that the Runtime Configurator is reachable by the Experiment Execution Manager (simulated with a fake-client based in Robot Framework [4]), trying to execute a Robot Framework [4] script related to the execution of an Ansible [13] default playbook (print “Hello World”).
Test tools	Robot Framework [4] and Ansible [13]
Result	Passed.
Comments	Scripts used can be found here: https://github.com/5GEVE/5geve-rc/tree/master/hello_world
Details	-
Test 2 – SBI Interface	rc-sbi-if
Test purpose	This test intends to test the SBI between the Runtime Configurator and the VNFs/PNFs to be configured with Day-2 configurations.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4], Ansible [13] and VNFs
Result	Passed.
Comments	Scripts used can be found here: https://github.com/5GEVE/5geve-rc/tree/master/delay

<i>Details</i>	-
Test 3 – Complete workflow	rc-complete
<i>Test purpose</i>	This test composes the two previous tests. As a result, Experiment Execution Manager executes some templates of the Runtime Configurator, and the commands included there will configure several VNFs/PNFs.
<i>Test tools</i>	Robot Framework [4], Ansible [13] and VNFs
<i>Result</i>	Passed.
<i>Comments</i>	Scripts used can be found here: https://github.com/5GEVE/5geve-rc/tree/master/delay
<i>Details</i>	-

3.2.5.3 Result analysis

The results obtained in the test execution confirm the assumptions commented at the beginning of the chapter, verifying that Ansible is correctly triggered from an external call and that executes the expected commands that were defined in some customized Ansible playbooks used for this purpose.

Moreover, as Robot Framework was initially used in the interaction between the EEM and the RC (it is based now in a REST API, as discussed in [3]), it has been really easy to integrate the Robot Framework logic in this set of tests.

3.2.6 Adaptation Layer test suites

The Multi-Site NSO to local Orchestrator interface (MSO-LO) is the portion of the Adaptation Layer that enables the I/W Framework to access the orchestration features provided by the trial sites involved in the 5G EVE project. The MSO-LO interface consists of a REST API exposed to the Interworking Layer and a series of drivers implemented to interact with local orchestrators of different technologies. The specification of features, requirements and a textual description of the API's methods are provided in D3.2 [15], while implementation details are presented in D3.3 [14].

In D3.6 [1], the plan and expected results of unit tests for this component were reported². As the MSO-LO interface is intended to interact with local NFVOs, the unit tests were executed by mocking their behaviour. The mocking has been useful to ensure the correctness of requests and response of the MSO-LO interface toward the specific NFVO interface. Anyway, mocked components cannot emulate completely the behaviour and conditions of a real instance of a NFVO, like authentication, waiting time for the instantiation of termination of a Network Service and more. The tests presented here are aimed at repeating the unit tests in a realistic deployment environment in the attempt to spot errors and unexpected behaviour that is not possible to capture with unit tests. We define them as integration tests, since they test the MSO-LO functionalities in an environment integrating other components of the Interworking Framework.

3.2.6.1 Test configuration, scenario and execution

Two test suites have been performed for the Adaptation Layer. The first test concerns the MSO-LO integration in Turin using ONAP and OSM local orchestrator; the second is the test of a new driver that interacts with a new local orchestrator running in the Italian site called EVER. As the tests are different each type of test suite is described in a specific Subsection.

3.2.6.2 MSO-LO integration test suite

The MSO-LO integration tests have been performed with two configuration setups:

1. Manual execution of the tests during the “Integration meeting” in January 2020 in Turin (codename MSO-LO-Turin).

² In Annex B, the detailed results of the unit test can be also found.

2. Automatic execution of the tests using Robot Framework [4] (codename MSO-LO-RF).

In configuration MSO-LO-Turin, the interactions with both ONAP and OSM orchestrators have been tested. The ONAP instance was hosted on ORA-PL premises, while the OSM instance was hosted on CNIT premises in Turin. The MSO-LO was deployed in CNIT premises in Turin in production configuration with Docker containers. The availability of the two orchestrators allowed us to test the whole functionality of the south-bound interface of the MSO-LO. On the other side, the MSO-LO API was triggered directly by the MSNO, testing the functionality of the north-bound part of the MSO-LO and completing the integration. Finally, in this configuration MSO-LO includes a local database to store information about the NFV Orchestrators registered on the 5G EVE platform.

Figure 7: MSO-LO-Turin configuration for Adaptation Layer tests

Figure 7 shows a graphical representation for MSO-LO-Turin configuration. Components outside the scope of the adaptation layer are coloured in dark grey. The MSNO is deployed in the same subnetwork as the MSO-LO, while the orchestrators, deployed in other data centres, are accessed through a VPN connection.

In configuration MSO-LO-RF, Robot Framework [4] scripts perform the testing workflow automatically. They implement triggers and waiting functions to deal with real instances of NFV orchestrators. This configuration also tests the interactions with the IWF Repository, an external storage component substituting the local database in the previous configuration. Figure 8 shows a graphical representation for MSO-LO-RF configuration.

Figure 8: MSO-LO-RF configuration for Adaptation Layer tests

3.2.6.3 EVER driver test suite

The EVER driver tests follow the test organization of other drivers (ONAP, OSM) and use the same tool described in D3.6 [1]. Specifically, they are planned to perform in three steps:

1. EVER driver unit test (codename EVER-unit-test).
2. EVER driver RF integration test (codename EVER-RF-integration-test).
3. EVER driver IWL integration test (codename EVER-IWL-integration-test).

The EVER-unit-test is shown in Figure 9 and verifies that the EVER driver sends correct information through the EVER NBI. In this configuration a Python script (PyTest) is created to send data to EVER driver via MSO-LO interface. The EVER driver formats such data according the EVER NBI interface. The formatted data are received and validated by a mock server done via Prism [20]. This test is executed in ERI-IT premises.

Figure 9: EVER-unit-test configuration

The EVER-RF-integration-test configuration is shown in Figure 10. This test verifies the interaction of the driver with the EVER orchestrator. In such configuration Robot Framework [4] is used to execute the test automatically and all command of EVER-unit-test are replicated in order to assert the correct work of the EVER orchestrator. This test is executed in ERI-IT premises.

Figure 10: EVER-RF-integration-test configuration

The EVER-IWL-integration-test configuration is shown in Figure 11. This test verifies the interaction of EVER driver and orchestrator with all IWL components running in Turin (like MSNO and Site Inventory). For such scope the EVER orchestrator will be placed in the Italian site and all command executed in the previous tests will be replicated to assert the interworking with IWL component.

Figure 11: EVER-IWL-test configuration

EVER orchestrator handles connectivity services (e.g. Radio and Transport resources to provide connectivity for vertical applications running in datacentre site) and requires additional network service parameters to handle RAN slice according 3GPP standards [21] [22]. As such extension will be implemented in Q3 inside IWL, the EVER-RF-integration-test and EVER-IWL-integration-test will be executed later and the results will be reported in the next Deliverable D3.5 [2].

3.2.6.4 Test results

According the description the results of MSO-LO integration tests and the result of EVER driver tests will be reported in each Subsection.

3.2.6.5 MSO-LO integration test results

Table 35 reports results from the configuration codenamed MSO-LO-Turin together with a summarized description of comments, encountered errors and actions to fix them. More details can be found in Annex B.

Table 35: Test summary for MSO-LO in configuration MSO-LO-Turin

MSO-LO – Configuration MSO-LO-Turin	
Test 1 - NFVO information integration test	
	Int-mso-lo-nfvo
<i>Test purpose</i>	Assert the correct retrieval of NFVO information from local database.
<i>Test tools</i>	None
<i>Result</i>	Passed
<i>Comments</i>	MSNO is sending us requests with double slashes in paths (e.g., //nfvo/). Not a problem, it works anyway. Applies to all other tests.
<i>Details</i>	-
Test 2 - OSM driver integration test	
	Int-mso-lo-osm
<i>Test purpose</i>	Assert that the request bodies sent to OSM NBI interface are correct. Assert that responses from OSM are handled correctly. Assert that responses returned by Mso-Lo API are correct.

Test tools	None
Result	Passed
Comments	Encountered mismatch between NSD identifiers.
Details	OSM uses the NSD package ID in the "nsdId" field of the request. The MSNO provides the NSD ID. This of course generates a 404 response at the moment of the instantiation request. We fixed this in the OSM driver, by swapping IDs when needed.
Test 3 - ONAP driver integration test	
	Int-mso-lo-onap
Test purpose	Assert that the request bodies sent to ONAP NBI interface are correct. Assert that responses from ONAP are handled correctly. Assert that responses returned by Mso-Lo API are correct.
Test tools	None
Result	Passed
Comments	Encountered timeout problems due to synchronous requests on ONAP side.
Details	Requests for instantiation and termination are asynchronous according to the ETSI NFV SOL 005 standard, while ONAP performs some operations in a synchronous fashion. Once the problem has been identified, the ONAP driver has been updated to adapt its behaviour to the previously mentioned standard reference. The issue was solved in place, making the final test execution successful.

Table 36 reports results from the configuration codenamed MSO-LO-RF together with a summarized description of comments, encountered errors and actions to fix them. More details can be found here: https://github.com/5GEVE/D3.7-Test-Suites-Results/tree/master/component_tests/adaptation_layer

Table 36: Test summary for MSO-LO in configuration MSO-LO-RF

MSO-LO – Configuration MSO-LO-RF	
Test 1 - NFVO information integration test	
	Int-mso-lo-nfvo
Test purpose	Assert the correct retrieval of NFVO information from local database.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4]
Result	Passed
Comments	Script name: MSO-LO-NFVO-Workflow.robot
Details	-
Test 2 – Subscriptions and notifications integration test	
	Int-mso-lo-onap
Test purpose	<i>Subscriptions:</i> Assert that the request bodies sent to Site Inventory interface are correct. Assert that responses from Site Inventory are handled correctly. Assert that responses returned by Mso-Lo API are correct. <i>Notifications:</i> Assert that request bodies sent to Mso-Lo notifications endpoint are correct. Assert acceptance of the notification and eventual forwarding to subscribed clients.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4], Python HTTP server to receive and log notifications
Result	Passed
Comments	Script name: MSO-LO-SUBS.robot
Details	The RF script tests all operations for the management of subscriptions and notifications checking both correct and incorrect behaviour.
Test 3 - OSM driver integration test	
	Int-mso-lo-osm
Test purpose	Assert that the request bodies sent to OSM NBI interface are correct. Assert that responses from OSM are handled correctly. Assert that responses returned by Mso-Lo API are correct.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4], Python HTTP server to receive and log notifications

Result	Passed
Comments	Script name: MSO-LO-LCM-Workflow.robot
Details	The RF script implements a complete testing workflow going from the creation to the deletion of a network service instance. It also includes the contextual tests for creating and deleting subscriptions. Tests also include additional instantiation parameters supported by the OSM driver.
Test 4 - ONAP driver integration test	
	Int-mso-lo-onap
Test purpose	Assert that the request bodies sent to ONAP NBI interface are correct. Assert that responses from ONAP are handled correctly. Assert that responses returned by Mso-Lo API are correct.
Test tools	Robot Framework [4], Python HTTP server to receive and log notifications
Result	Passed
Comments	Script name: MSO-LO-LCM-Workflow.robot
Details	The RF script implements a complete testing workflow going from the creation to the deletion of a network service instance. It also includes the contextual tests for creating and deleting subscriptions.

3.2.6.6 EVER driver test results

Table 37 reports results from the EVER driver test suite. The table reports first the test case associated to the configuration described above, according to the format proposed in D3.6 [1], and then the results together with a summarized description of comments and details.

Table 37: Test summary for EVER driver Test suite

MSO-LO – Configuration MSO-LO-Ever	
Test 1 – EVER driver Test Unit	unit-mso-lo-ever
Test purpose	Assert that the request bodies sent to EVER NBI interface are correct. Assert that responses from EVER NBI are handled correctly. Assert that responses returned by Mso-Lo API are correct. EVER server is mocked with Prism and the OpenAPI specification of EVER NBI
Test Type	Functional
Related tests	-
Priority	High
Execution Time	5-10 seconds
Test tools	Manual (via Docker Compose)
Configuration	EVER-unit-test
References	MSO-LO Interface OpenAPI – D3.4 [3].
Applicability	-
Pre-test conditions	Prism mock server running with EVER NBI OpenAPI specification.
Test Sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Check status codes 201, 400, headers and payload for POST /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances. 2. Check status code 200 headers and payload for GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances. 3. Check status codes 200, 404, headers and payload for GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}. 4. Check status codes 204, 404, headers and payload for DELETE /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}. 5. Check status codes 202, 400, 404, headers and payload for POST /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instance/{nsInstanceId}/stantiate.

	<p>6. Check status codes 202, 404, headers and payload for POST /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instance/{nsInstanceId}/terminate.</p> <p>7. Check status code 201 headers and payload for GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ ns_lcm_op_occs.</p> <p>8. Check status codes 200, 404, headers and payload for GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_lcm_op_occs/{lcm_id}</p>
Expected Results	All assertion verified. No errors
Test 1 – Execution	
	unit-mso-lo-ever
Result	Passed
Comments	-
Details	-
Test 2 – EVER driver Integration	
	ever-driver-integration
Test purpose	Assert that the request bodies sent to EVER NBI interface are correct. Assert that responses from EVER are handled correctly. Assert that responses returned by Mso-Lo API are correct.
Test type	Integration
Related tests	-
Priority	High
Execution time	2 minutes
Test tools	Automatically via Robot Framework [4]
Configuration	EVER-RF-integration-test
References	-
Applicability	-
Pre-test conditions	“Ever driver test unit” correctly executed
Test sequence	Same sequence of test 1 is replicated and executed via Robot Framework [4].
Expected results	All assertion verified. Robot Framework [4] result with no error. EVER internal database correctly filled
Test 2 – Execution	
	ever-driver-integration
Result	Not executed
Comments	Need RAN service slice extension in MSO-LO interface
Details	Planned to be executed in Q3 2020 and reported in D3.5 [2].
Test 3 – EVER site integration	
	ever-site-integration
Test purpose	Assert that IWL request bodies sent to EVER NBI interface are correct. Assert that responses from EVER are handled correctly by IWL component. Assert that radio and transport infrastructure in Italian site are correctly configured.
Test type	Integration
Related tests	-
Priority	Medium
Execution time	5-10 minutes
Test tools	Automatically (via MSNO)
Configuration	-

References	-
Applicability	-
Pre-test conditions	“EVER driver integration test” and “EVER driver unit test” correctly executed
Test sequence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Configure in IWL the vertical service using Italian site. 2. MSNO send messages to create and instantiate the service to EVER 3. EVER configures the service 4. EVER sends affirmative response 5. Service is registered in IWL and relative network service and life-cycle management info can be retrieved.
Expected results	Network Service instantiated and running in EVER. Info about the services can be retrieved
Test 3 – Execution	ever-site-integration
Result	Not executed
Comments	Need RAN service slice extension in MSO-LO interface
Details	Planned to be executed in Q3 2020 and reported in D3.5 [2].

3.2.6.7 Result analysis

The adaptation layer integration tests implementation and execution has been challenging due to the many interactions with other components. In fact, the Adaptation Layer acts as a bridge connecting NFV Orchestrators hosted at sites with the IWL, in particular the Multi-Site Orchestrator.

The integration tests performed in Turin (Configuration MSO-LO-Turin) highlighted some issues impossible to identify in the development environment. In particular, we identified the OSM distinction between “nsdId” and “nsdPackageId” and fixed their management in the relevant driver. We also dealt with problems due to synchronous and asynchronous operations and relevant delays and waiting times that needed to be managed. The tests were extremely useful to define and adjust the next steps and strategy for the development of the MSO-LO interface.

The Robot Framework [4] tests were developed with the goal to replicate the tests performed manually in Turin. With the environment in place and the correct configuration, the RF scripts can perform autonomously complete workflows of operations including dynamic reconfiguration of variables, waiting times, checking of HTTP status codes and response bodies. The added value of using Robot Framework [4] is the full automation of the tests: replicating the tests performed during an entire day in Turin takes just 4-5 minutes with RF scripts.

Once RF scripts were in place, we also used them constantly during the development of new features. Taking just few minutes and covering the majority of our application code, re-running tests allowed us to immediately spot new bugs and fix them before releasing new versions.

Regarding the EVER driver test has been executed and no particular challenge is encountered. In any case, the test is very basic and simple. Some challenge is expected with the other tests and the relative analysis will be reported in D3.5 [2] when will be executed.

3.3 Integration Tests between Interworking Framework components

The integration tests need to be executed in certain identified integration points to verify that these transactions within the I/W Framework are working as expected. However, as stated in Table 2 of Section 1.1, most of the I/W Framework components tests require integration between several components to validate their functionality. So, the number of tests listed in section 3.2 covers most of the integration test scope.

Then, the execution of a set of integration test between the Multi-Site NSO and the Multi-Site Catalogue is the only integration test executed specifically under the scope of integration tests and it is presented in this section.

3.3.1 NSO-Catalogue integration

As commented above, MSNO and MS Catalogue are key components of the IWL and for that reason we introduce an integration test in this document. As core principle, we reuse the component tests of the northern element of the integration test as test suite for the integration.

3.3.1.1 Test configuration, scenario and execution

For these integration test, we will use a standard configuration of the IWL, where we deploy the real components to be tested, MSNO and MS Catalogue, and we test them using the NBI of the MSNO.

3.3.1.2 Test results

In this case, we use the component test of MSNO described in 3.2.3, so no new test cases have to be defined in this context. The results are present in Table 38:

Table 38: Multi-Site Network Orchestrator-Catalogue test results

Multi-Site Network Orchestrator-Catalogue	
Test 1 - Network Service ID creation	
	ms-nso-id-creation
<i>Test purpose</i>	The purpose of this test is to validate the creation of a Network Service ID. This is the first step for deploying a Network Service
<i>Test tools</i>	Robot Framework [4]
<i>Result</i>	Passed
<i>Comments</i>	The original design of this test assumed that the onboarding of a NS into the IWL will raise an onboarding in the 5G-EVE sites. In the final implementation the onboarding of the NS into the sites is done in the Instantiation operation and for this reason the checking is moved to Test 2
<i>Details</i>	-
Test 2 – Network Service instantiation	
	ms-nso-ns-inst
<i>Test purpose</i>	This test aims to verify the instantiation of a Network Service in a specific 5G-EVE site
<i>Test tools</i>	Robot Framework [4]
<i>Result</i>	Passed
<i>Comments</i>	-
<i>Details</i>	-
Test 3 – Network Service Lifecycle Management	
	ms-nso-ns-lcm
<i>Test purpose</i>	The purpose of this test is to validate the lifecycle management of the Network Services.
<i>Test tools</i>	Robot Framework [4]
<i>Result</i>	Passed
<i>Comments</i>	Some features included in this test are not supported yet, like update and scale operations. They are postponed.
<i>Details</i>	-
Test 4 – Network Service Lifecycle Management notifications	
	ms-nso-ns-lcm-not
<i>Test purpose</i>	The purpose of this test is to validate the MSNO notifications.
<i>Test tools</i>	Robot Framework [4]
<i>Result</i>	Not executed

Comments	These tests are planned in the roadmap to be done when IWL supports external notifications.
Details	-

3.3.1.3 Result analysis

The results of the test demonstrate the great effort that we did in the integration of the IWL components. The automation of the tests using Robot Framework [4] allows us to easily check the status of the IWL after a change or a source code update.

3.4 Interworking Layer System Tests

In this section, the testing of the inter-site connectivity is presented.

3.4.1 Site facilities' interconnection

The site facilities tests aim at validating the connectivity between Sites included in 5G-EVE Platform (French, Spanish, Italian, Greek) with Interworking Layer. Inter-connectivity allows the communication of embedded IWL systems (e.g. Multi-Site Network Orchestrator, Multi-Site Catalogue, Runtime Configurator etc.) with sites. As the topology of 5G EVE's interconnection is a star in the orchestration plane, with the I/W Framework deployed in the centre of the star, the connectivity testing on this plane will be focused on ensuring that the I/W Framework's modules implementing a SBI can reach each of the sites via the VPN interconnections. For this, specific IP address ranges must be defined per site, which should be reachable via ping³ from the site at Turin.

3.4.1.1 Test configuration, scenario and execution

The interconnection tests carried out so far have been performed in two main setups:

- Manual connectivity tests executed by triggering ping operations manually. Operations have been executed in both ways: starting from IWL servers and each local Site
- Manual connectivity tests executed by generating randomized traffic using iperf⁴ tool.

3.4.1.2 Test results

The following tables provide a summary of interconnection test results, following the template described in section 3.1 and the test plan reported in D3.6 [1]. Note that the tests reported in this deliverable are not exactly the same as the ones described in D3.6 [1], only focusing on ping and iperf tests as a more efficient testing method which also allow remote testing (necessary due to COVID19). In any case, the final results of these tests will be reported in D3.5 [2].

Table 39: Interworking Layer – French Site test results

IWL - French Site	
Test 1 – Interworking Layer – French Site	
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying the VPN between Turin Lab where IWL is deployed and Paris – Chatillon lab where located is a base of French Site and main point of contact for most of IWL systems. Test has been executed sending small packets of information containing an ICMP simple message using ping tools.
Test tools	Ping

³ <https://ping.com/en-us/>

⁴ <https://iperf.fr/>

Result	Passed
Comments	Requested inter-connection latency: 60 ms. Measured latency: 42.7 ms in average.
Details	-
Test 2 – Interworking Layer – French Site	
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying the VPN between Turin Lab where IWL is deployed and Paris – Chatillon lab where is a base of French Site and main point of contact for most of IWL systems. Test has been executed sending random traffic using iperf as a traffic generator
Test tools	Iperf
Result	Passed
Comments	Some basic connectivity tests were executed, more detailed performance tests will be reported in D3.5 [2].
Details	-

Table 40: Interworking Layer – Spanish Site test results

IWL - Spanish Site	
Test 1 – Interworking Layer – Spanish Site	
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying the VPN between Turin Lab where IWL is deployed and Madrid (Spain) lab where located is a base of French Site and main point of contact of most of IWL systems. Test has been executed sending a small packet of information containing an ICMP simple message using ping tools.
Test tools	Ping
Result	Passed
Comments	Requested inter-connection latency: 110 ms. Measured latency: 55 ms in average.
Details	-
Test 2 – Interworking Layer – Spanish Site	
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying the VPN between Turin Lab where IWL is deployed and Madrid lab where a base of Spanish Site is located and main point of contact for most of IWL systems. Test has been executed sending random traffic using iperf as a traffic generator
Test tools	Iperf
Result	Passed
Comments	Some basic connectivity tests were executed, more detailed performance tests will be reported in D3.5 [2].
Details	-

Table 41: Interworking Layer – Italian Site test results

IWL - Italian Site	
Test 1 – Interworking Layer – Italian Site	
Test purpose	This test aims at verifying the VPN between Turin Lab where IWL is deployed and Turin/Rome lab where located is a base of Italian Site and main point of contact for most of IWL systems. Test has been executed sending a small packet of information containing an ICMP simple message using ping tools.
Test tools	Ping
Result	Passed

<i>Comments</i>	Requested inter-connection latency: none. Measured latency: 26.5 ms in average.
<i>Details</i>	-
Test 2 – Interworking Layer – Italian Site	
<i>Test purpose</i>	This test aims at verifying the VPN between Turin Lab where IWL is deployed and Turin/Rome lab where a base of Italian Site is located and main point of contact for most for IWL systems. Test has been executed sending random traffic using iperf as a traffic generator
<i>Test tools</i>	Iperf
<i>Result</i>	Passed
<i>Comments</i>	Some basic connectivity tests were executed, more detailed performance tests will be reported in D3.5 [2].
<i>Details</i>	-

Table 42: Interworking Layer – Greek Site test results

IWL - Greek Site	
Test 1 – Interworking Layer – Greek Site	
<i>Test purpose</i>	This test aims at verifying the VPN between Turin Lab where IWL is deployed and Athens where located is a base of Greek Site and main point of contact for most of IWL systems. Test has been executed sending a small packet of information containing an ICMP simple message using ping tools.
<i>Test tools</i>	Ping
<i>Result</i>	Passed
<i>Comments</i>	Requested inter-connection latency: 160 ms. Measured latency: 70.9 ms in average.
<i>Details</i>	-
Test 2 – Interworking Layer – Greek Site	
<i>Test purpose</i>	This test aims at verifying the VPN between Turin Lab where IWL is deployed and Athens lab where a base of Greek Site is located and main point of contact for most for IWL systems. Test has been executed sending random traffic using iperf as a traffic generator
<i>Test tools</i>	Iperf
<i>Result</i>	Passed
<i>Comments</i>	Some basic connectivity tests were executed, more detailed performance tests will be reported in D3.5 [2].
<i>Details</i>	-

3.4.1.3 Result analysis

Simple interconnection tests have been executed between IWL and each of the local sites. Both ping and iperf traffic reachability confirmed proper VPN tunnels establishment. Some small delay in creating connection has appeared as a result of COVID19 and lack of physical access to labs. However, connectivity of each of Sites with IWL lab in Turin has been confirmed up for now.

The results regarding latency between sites are better than expected, improving our initial expectation detailed in D3.2 [15]:

Figure 12: Latency between sites and the IWL

- Regarding bandwidth and availability, the tests have not been completed due to the COVID-19 situation, but preliminary results are promising. The results are: French intra-suite communication meets the expectations of data plane interconnection defined in D3.2, with a bandwidth between 300 and 400 Mbps
- Inter-site connectivity between the 5G EVE sites are between 40 and 80 Mbps. This result meets the requirements for a control plane interconnectivity

We plan to include more detailed results in the next deliverable (D3.5 [2]).

4 Overall analysis of test results

This section presents in detail the overall analysis of test results presented in the previous sections.

4.1 Acceptance criteria

The executed test suites and test cases reported in this deliverable focused mainly on the validation of individual (IWL Component and Integration of components) as well as overall functionality (IWL System) of the Interworking Framework. Since the focus of the I/W Framework testing is mainly on the functional perspective rather than performance, there is no quantitative criteria defined to accept/validate the reported test results. The acceptance of each test is based mainly on the comparison of results with the expected outcome or goal defined in D3.6 [1] along with the appropriate test configuration.

4.2 Overall test assessment

This section summarizes the overall test assessment reported in section 3. The test assessment is carried out separately for different test categories such as Component, Integration and System tests. As stated in Section 4.1, the assessment mainly used the defined objective of each test to validate the test as well as the functionality of I/W Framework. The overall test assessment is carried out separately for different test categories such as Component, Integration and System tests.

Table 43 presents the summary of the Interworking Layer tests cases along with the number of passed, failed and pending tests.

Table 43: Summary of test cases execution

Test	Test Suites	Test Summary		
		Number of Passed Tests	Number of Failed Tests	Number of pending Tests
Component Tests				
Multi-Site Catalogue Test Suites	Multi-Site Catalogue – NSD Management	6		9
	Multi-Site Catalogue – VNF Management	2	-	4
	Multi-Site Catalogue – PNFD Management	-	-	6
Multi-Site Inventory Test Suites	Multi-Site Inventory – Write Operation	3	-	1
	Multi-Site Inventory – Query Operation	2	-	1
Multi-Site Network Orchestrator Test Suites	Multi-Site Network Orchestrator	3	-	1
Data Collection Manager Test Suites	Data Collection Manager Kafka	5	-	-
	Data Collection Manager Kafka – ELK Interconnection – NBI	1	-	-

	Data Collection Manager Kafka – Filebeat Interconnection – SBI	2	-	-
Runtime Configurator Test Suites	Runtime Configurator	3	-	-
Adaptation Layer Test Suites	MSO-LO – Configuration MSO-LO-Turin	3	-	-
	MSO-LO – Configuration MSO-LO-RF	4	-	-
	MSO-LO – Configuration MSO-LO-Ever	1	-	2
Integration Tests				
NSO-Catalogue integration	Multi-Site Network Orchestrator-Catalogue	3	-	1
System Tests				
Site-facilities’ interconnection Test Suites	IWL – French Site	2	-	-
	IWL – Spanish Site	2	-	-
	IWL – Italian Site	2	-	-
	IWL – Greek Site	2	-	-

It is important to highlight that the outbreak of the Coronavirus pandemic in the beginning of 2020 also had an impact on 5G-EVE activities, both on single and multi-site use cases. To meet project expectations and, at the same time, to consider pandemic restrictions, remote working procedures have been widely used by many partners. However, there was a significant setback on some of the implementation and testing activities; especially those involving multiple components, multiple sites and multiple partners. Due to this unexpected event, those test cases which cannot be completed as planned for this deliverable have been moved to the next deliverable of WP3 (D3.5 [2]), as stated in the following lines.

4.2.1 Component Tests Assessment

- **Multi-Site Catalogue tests:** this deliverable reports only the results of Multi-Site Catalogue validated against ETSI OSM local-site orchestrators, as the support and integration with ONAP local site orchestrators is still in progress and will be reported in the final D3.5 [2] deliverable. This test in summary validated a) an NSD modelling a vertical experiment can be onboarded, updated and deleted in the Multi-Site Catalogue from its NBI as well as the specific per-site OSM orchestrator, b) an NSD modelling a single-site service can be successfully onboarded, updated and deleted in the Multi-Site Catalogue through the SBI from a specific per-site OSM orchestrator, and c) an NSD modelling a vertical experiment can be onboarded, and deleted in the Multi-Site Catalogue from its NBI as well as the specific per-site OSM and ONAP orchestrator simultaneously
- **Multi-Site Inventory tests:** this test in general aims to validate the write and query feature of Multi-Site Inventory when the operation is initiated by the Multi-Site NSO. Most of the test results leading to Multi-Site Inventory test suites are in progress and will be reported in D3.5 [2]. Apart from those test in progress, there are number of test related to write operation such as NSI scaling at single site and NSI update at single site are found to be not in scope of the I/W Framework current features especially with the feature of Multi Site NSO.
- **Multi-Site Network Orchestrator tests:** this test suite in general aims at validating the operation of Multi-Site Network Orchestrator functionality. Most of the test results leading to Multi-Site Orchestrator test suites are in progress and will be reported in D3.5 [2].

- **Data Collection Manager tests:** this deliverable reports the results of all the test planned (in D3.6 [1]) for validating the functionality of Data Collection Manager. This test in summary validated all the features of Data Collection Manager such as Data Collection Manager-Kafka operations, ELK Interconnection (NBI) and Filebeat interconnection (SBI) as defined in section 1.1.
- **Runtime Configurator tests:** this deliverable reports the results all the test planned (in D3.6 [1]) for validating the functionality of the Runtime Configurator. The test results validated all the specified features of the Runtime Configurator such as NBI, SBI and the complete workflow.
- **Adaptation Layer tests:** this deliverable reports the results of all the test planned (in D3.6 [1]) for validating the functionality of the Adaptation Layer. This test results validated all the expected features of adaptation layer such as a) the correct retrieval of NFVO information from local database, b) the correct retrieval and creation of subscriptions for notifications about the NS instance status, and c) the request bodies sent to ONAP and OSM NBI interface are correct, the responses from ONAP and OSM are handled correctly and the responses returned by Mso-Lo API are correct.

4.2.2 Integration Tests Assessment

The execution of the Integration tests between the Multi-Site NSO and the Multi-Site Catalogue is the only Integration test executed specifically under the scope of Integration tests and it is presented in this deliverable. This is due to the fact that many of the component test require also Integration test between other components to validate their functionality and is reported in their respective component test section.

4.2.3 System Tests Assessment

The System tests aim at validating the entire I/W Framework and components (eg. Multi-Site Network Orchestrator, Multi-Site Catalogue, Runtime Configurator, etc.). The connectivity or interconnection tests has been executed between the IWL deployed at Turin site and other sites (French, Spanish, Italian and Greek) included in the 5G-EVE platform definition. Successful ping and iperf traffic reachability were achieved in each test, with proper VPN tunnels established between sites.

4.3 Impact of test environment

Since the focus of the I/W Framework testing is mainly on the functional perspective rather than the performance, the impact of test environment is out of scope for I/W Framework test suites. There is just only one performance test reported within this testing process, which is the load testing done in the Data Collection Manager, whose results can be extrapolated to the future production environment in which the I/W Framework is expected to be deployed. Regarding that load testing process within the DCM, the results fulfilled the expectations in the designed platform, so that solution should work properly in the final implementation of the I/W Framework.

However, as discussed in section 2.3.2 and in the beginning of this section, there is a considerable impact (in terms of delay) from COVID-19 for executing tests involving multiple sites along with involvement and coordination between several partners.

5 Conclusions

This is the second and final deliverable in T3.4 related to the execution of Interworking test suites, already defined in D3.6 [1]. This deliverable presents in detail the outcomes of all the tests executed with respect to the I/W Framework components and capabilities. This deliverable further presents also the overall analysis of the test results.

The main scope of the I/W Framework testing is to test and validate the I/W Framework itself, as an independent system. As presented in D3.6 [1], there are three kind of test categories, such as Component Tests (also known as Unit Test to test each components in the I/W Framework), Integration Tests (to test integration between different I/W components) and System Tests (to test the whole I/W Framework), which are executed to validate the I/W Framework, also aligned with the different testing standards discussed in D3.6 [1]. The testing of I/W Framework followed software testing principles and strategies present in most software development projects along with ETSI standard specifications.

During the testing process, apart from performing the test cases in separate, private testbeds, each of them belonging to each partner involved in the design and deployment of the I/W Framework, a complete I/W Framework testing environment was deployed on the Spanish site facility, in order to allow more flexibility on the partners working on each component of the I/W Framework in their corresponding tests and also in the integration with the 5G EVE Portal, which is located in the Spanish site. In the end, the IWL will be installed in the Italian site, as it was stated in the deliverable D3.2 [15]; however, at the time of finishing this deliverable, this deployment is still pending due to some final issues to be checked regarding the multi-site connectivity process.

Since there is a high degree of interaction between I/W Framework components using REST APIs, API-testing tools are used. Among the list of state-of-the-art API testing tools, Robot Framework [4] was selected and used for execution of automated testing. The test results are reported in the 5G EVE Github repository located at <https://github.com/5GEVE/D3.7-Test-Suites-Results>.

The number of I/W Framework Component Tests covered most of the integration test scope, as stated before. The execution of Integration Tests between the Multi-Site NSO and the Multi-Site Catalogue is the only integration test executed specifically under the scope of integration tests. The connectivity or interconnection tests has been executed between IWL deployed at Turin site and other sites (French, Spanish, Italian and Greek) included in the 5G EVE Platform definition, and also, successful ping and iperf traffic reachability were achieved in each test, using proper VPN tunnels established between sites.

The outbreak of the Coronavirus pandemic in the beginning of 2020 also had an impact on 5G EVE activities. It caused an unexpected delay in 25 test cases, which will be reported in D3.5 [2]. But, despite the pandemic impact a total of 46 test cases were passed and no failed test cases were detected, so the testing process has been able to overcome this hard moment with good results, overall.

To meet project expectations and, at the same time, to take into account pandemic restrictions, a new subchapter with COVID-19 risks is included in this deliverable, defining COVID-19 risks identified in single and multi-site scenarios. The updated testing roadmap along with completed tests and future tests to be reported in D3.5 [2] are also presented in this deliverable.

Acknowledgment

This project has received funding from the EU H2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 815074.

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Annex A. Detailed additional test cases for Multi-Site Inventory

As stated in section 3.2.2, there are two tests that have been additionally included in this document compared with D3.6 [1], for the Multi-Site Inventory. Both have to do with operations (write or query) over non-existent NSI, so that appropriate error handling is ensured.

The following are the detailed test case descriptions complementing those originally included in D3.6 [1]:

Table 44: Multi-Site Inventory – Write Operation missing test cases

Multi-Site Inventory – Write Operation	
Test 9 – Non-existing NSI	write-nsi-lifecycle-non-existing
<i>Test purpose</i>	This test aims at verifying that appropriate error handling is done in case the Multi-Site NSO tries a write operation over a non-existing NSI index at the Multi-Site Inventory.
<i>Test type</i>	Functional
<i>Related tests</i>	None
<i>Priority</i>	High
<i>Execution time</i>	As required for the full test execution
<i>Configuration</i>	MSNO_MSI_CONF
<i>References</i>	Operations over inventories/databases can follow multiple standards; specific references may be provided depending on the implementation decision. NS lifecycle is governed by ETSI NFV SOL005.
<i>Applicability</i>	Multi-Site Inventory to Multi-Site NSO interface
<i>Pre-test conditions</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A Multi-Site NSO instance is available and with communication to the Multi-Site Inventory
<i>Test sequence</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> The Multi-Site NSO sends a termination operation to the Multi-Site Inventory using a NSI index which is not active The response from the Multi-Site Inventory is evaluated Status of the Multi-Site Inventory is checked
<i>Expected results</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> An error message is sent from Multi-Site Inventory to Multi-Site NSO The Multi-Site Inventory is still up and running and has not crashed

Table 45: Multi-Site Inventory – Query Operation missing test cases

Multi-Site Inventory – Query Operation	
Test 3 – Non-existing NSI status	query-non-existing
<i>Test purpose</i>	This test aims at verifying that appropriate error handling is done in case the Multi-Site NSO requests information about a non-existing NSI index at the Multi-Site Inventory.
<i>Test type</i>	Functional
<i>Related tests</i>	None
<i>Priority</i>	High
<i>Execution time</i>	As required for the full test execution
<i>Configuration</i>	MSNO_MSI_CONF
<i>References</i>	Operations over inventories/databases can follow multiple standards; specific references may be provided depending on the implementation decision. Attributes included in the NS LoI are governed by ETSI NFV SOL005.

<i>Applicability</i>	Multi-Site Inventory to Multi-Site NSO interface
<i>Pre-test conditions</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• A Multi-Site NSO instance is available and with communication to the Multi-Site Inventory
<i>Test sequence</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. The Multi-Site NSO sends a query operation to the Multi-Site Inventory using a NSI index which is not active2. The response from the Multi-Site Inventory is evaluated3. Status of the Multi-Site Inventory is checked
<i>Expected results</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. An error message is sent from Multi-Site Inventory to Multi-Site NSO2. The Multi-Site Inventory is still up and running and has not crashed

Annex B. Detailed test cases' report for MSO-LO tests

In this Annex, the Integration tests performed in Turin facilities for the MSO-LO tests (MSO_LO_TURIN configuration) are presented, based on a deployment of the 5G EVE Platform including the MSNO, IWF Repository, Adaptation Layer (MSO-LO), OSM + Opentsack, ONAP + Openstack. All software was running on premises at Politecnico of Turin, except for ONAP and Openstack, running in ORA-PL premises. The first results are included in Table 46. Red cells indicate test failure.

Table 46: NSO-LO tests in MSO_LO_TURIN configuration – complete test report (I)

Test Name	Test Description	Test Case	Result	Comment	Tested by (Partner Name)	Test Date
Test 1 – NFVO information integration test	Assert the correct retrieval of NFVO information from local database.	Request GET /nfvo. Check status code 200, headers, body response	OK	MSNO is sending us requests with double slashes in paths (e.g., //nfvo/). Not a problem, it works anyway. Applies to all other requests.	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 1 – NFVO information integration test	Assert the correct retrieval of NFVO information from local database.	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}. Check status code 200, headers, body response	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	Assert that the request bodies sent to OSM NBI interface are correct. Assert that responses from OSM are handled correctly. Assert that responses returned by Mso-Lo API are correct.					
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the list is empty.	~	Not used by MSNO at the moment	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request POST /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances. Check status code 201, headers, body response. Check the ns_instance resource creation in OSM.	OK	OSM uses the NSD package ID in the "nsdId" field of the request. The MSNO gives the NSD id. This of course generates a 404 response. We fixed this in the OSM driver in the Adaptation Layer, by swapping IDs when needed.	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}. Get the path from Location header from previous response. Check	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020

		status code 200, headers, body response. Check the new NS instance is returned.				
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the new NS instance is listed.	~	Not used by MSNO at the moment	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request POST /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}/instantiate. Check status code 202, headers, body response. Check the NS instance is instantiating in OSM.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}. Get the path from Location header from previous response. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the new NS instance is returned.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_lcm_op_ocs/{opId}. Get the path from Location header from previous response. Check status code 200, headers, body response.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_lcm_op_ocs. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the previous operation is listed.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request POST /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}/terminate. Check status code 202, headers, body response. Check the NS instance is terminating in OSM.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_lcm_op_ocs/{opId}. Get the path from Location header from previous response. Check status code 200, headers, body response.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_lcm_op_ocs. Check status code 200, headers, body response.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020

		Check the previous operation is listed.				
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request DELETE /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}. Check status code 202, headers, body response. Check the NS instance is removed from OSM.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	Assert that the request bodies sent to ONAP NBI interface are correct. Assert that responses from ONAP are handled correctly. Assert that responses returned by Mso-Lo API are correct. ONAP server is mocked with Prism and the OpenAPI specification of ONAP NBI.					
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the list is empty.	~	Not used by MSNO at the moment	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	24/01/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request POST /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances. Check status code 201, headers, body response. Check the ns_instance resource creation in OSM.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	24/01/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}. Get the path from Location header from previous response. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the new NS instance is returned.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	24/01/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the new NS instance is listed.	~	Not used by MSNO at the moment	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	24/01/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request POST /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}/instantiate. Check status code 202, headers, body response. Check the NS instance is instantiating in OSM.	FAIL	Timeout and 504 response. This request is synchronous when towards ONAP. We are fixing this.	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	24/01/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_lcm_op_ocs/{opId}. Get the path from Location header from previous response. Check	FAIL	Given the timeout problem, the MSNO can't get the operation ID. We could not test this.	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	24/01/2020

		status code 200, headers, body response.				
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_lcm_op_ocs. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the previous operation is listed.	~	Not used by MSNO at the moment	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	24/01/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request POST /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}/terminate. Check status code 202, headers, body response. Check the NS instance is terminating in OSM.	FAIL	Timeout and 504 response. This request is synchronous when towards ONAP. We are fixing this.	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	24/01/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_lcm_op_ocs/{opId}. Get the path from Location header from previous response. Check status code 200, headers, body response.	FAIL	Given the timeout problem, the MSNO can't get the operation ID. We could not test this.	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	24/01/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_lcm_op_ocs. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the previous operation is listed.	~	Not used by MSNO at the moment	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	24/01/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request DELETE /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}. Check status code 202, headers, body response. Check the NS instance is removed from OSM.	FAIL	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	24/01/2020

And now, Table 47 presents the Integration tests after fixing the failures presented in the last report.

Table 47: NSO-LO tests in MSO_LO_TURIN configuration – complete test report (II)

Test Name	Test Description	Test Case	Result	Comment	Tested by (Partner Name)	Test Date
Test 1 – NFVO information integration test	Assert the correct retrieval of NFVO information from local database.	Request GET /nfvo. Check status code 200, headers, body response	OK	MSNO is sending us requests with double slashes in paths (e.g., //nfvo/). Not a problem, it works anyway. Applies to all other requests.	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 1 – NFVO information integration test	Assert the correct retrieval of NFVO information	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}. Check status code 200, headers, body response	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020

	from local database.					
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	Assert that the request bodies sent to OSM NBI interface are correct. Assert that responses from OSM are handled correctly. Assert that responses returned by Mso-Lo API are correct.					
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the list is empty.	~	Not used by MSNO at the moment	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request POST /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances. Check status code 201, headers, body response. Check the ns_instance resource creation in OSM.	OK	OSM uses the NSD package ID in the "nsdId" field of the request. The MSNO gives the NSD id. This of course generates a 404 response. We fixed this in the OSM driver in the Adaptation Layer, by swapping IDs when needed.	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}. Get the path from Location header from previous response. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the new NS instance is returned.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the new NS instance is listed.	~	Not used by MSNO at the moment	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request POST /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}/instantiate. Check status code 202, headers, body response. Check the NS instance is instantiating in OSM.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}. Get the path from Location header from previous response. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the new NS instance is returned.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020

Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_lcm_op_o ccs/{opId}. Get the path from Location header from previous response. Check status code 200, headers, body response.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_lcm_op_o ccs. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the previous operation is listed.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request POST /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}/terminate. Check status code 202, headers, body response. Check the NS instance is terminating in OSM.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_lcm_op_o ccs/{opId}. Get the path from Location header from previous response. Check status code 200, headers, body response.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_lcm_op_o ccs. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the previous operation is listed.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – OSM driver integration test	-	Request DELETE /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}. Check status code 202, headers, body response. Check the NS instance is removed from OSM.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	23/01/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	Assert that the request bodies sent to ONAP NBI interface are correct. Assert that responses from ONAP are handled correctly. Assert that responses returned by Mso-Lo API are correct. ONAP server is mocked with Prism and the OpenAPI specification of ONAP NBI.					
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the list is empty.	~	Not used by MSNO at the moment	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	24/01/2020

Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request POST /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances. Check status code 201, headers, body response. Check the ns_instance resource creation in OSM.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	24/01/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}. Get the path from Location header from previous response. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the new NS instance is returned.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	24/01/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the new NS instance is listed.	~	Not used by MSNO at the moment	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	24/01/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request POST /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}/instantiate. Check status code 202, headers, body response. Check the NS instance is instantiating in OSM.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	18/02/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_lcm_op_ocs/{opId}. Get the path from Location header from previous response. Check status code 200, headers, body response.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	18/02/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_lcm_op_ocs. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the previous operation is listed.	~	Not used by MSNO at the moment	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	18/02/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request POST /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}/terminate. Check status code 202, headers, body response. Check the NS instance is terminating in OSM.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	18/02/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_lcm_op_ocs/{opId}. Get the path from Location header from previous response. Check status code 200, headers, body response.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	18/02/2020

Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request GET /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_lcm_op_ocs. Check status code 200, headers, body response. Check the previous operation is listed.	~	Not used by MSNO at the moment	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	18/02/2020
Test 3 – ONAP driver integration test	-	Request DELETE /nfvo/{nfvoId}/ns_instances/{nsInstanceId}. Check status code 202, headers, body response. Check the NS instance is removed from OSM.	OK	-	CNIT, ORA-PL, ERI-ES	18/02/2020